

分类号:

单位代码: 10389

密 级:

学 号: 2161904003

福建农林大学

博士学位论文

油橄榄叶痂病病原菌 (*Venturia oleaginea*) 的分离、生物学特性和基因组 分析

学科门类: 农学

一级学科名称: 植物保护

二级学科名称: 植物病理学

研究方向: 植物真菌学

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完成时间: 二〇二一年六月

**Isolation, biological characteristics and
genome sequencing of *Venturia oleaginea*, the
causal agent of olive leaf scab**

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A Dissertation Submitted to

College of Plant Protection

**Fujian Agriculture and Forestry University
in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for
Doctoral Degree in plant pathology
College of Plant Protection**

**Fujian Agriculture and Forestry University
Fujian, P.R. China**

Completion Date (June, 2021)

Commencement Date (September, 2016)

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学 院	PLANT PROTECTION		专 业	PLANT PATHOLOGY	
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授予学位级别	博士 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 硕士 <input type="checkbox"/>	授予学位时间	2021 年 6 月		
学位论文题目	Isolation, biological characteristics and genome sequencing of <i>Venturia oleaginea</i> , the causal agent of olive leaf scab				
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List of Abbreviations

ANOVA	Analysis of variance
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
CTAB	Cetyl trimethylammonium bromide
DAI	Days After Inoculation
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
ITS	Internal transcribed spacer
LSU	larger subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA
NAPAA	non-alpha poly-amino acids
NCBI	National Centre for Biotechnology Information
ng/rxn	nanogram/ chemical reaction
nrDNA	Nuclear ribosomal DNA
NRPS	Non-ribosomal peptide
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
RNase	Ribonuclease
SSU	Small subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA
T1PKS	Type I Polyketide synthase
TBE	Tris/Borate/EDTA
TEF1	Elongation factor-1 alpha
UV	Ultraviolet

摘要

油橄榄孔雀斑病，又称叶痂病，是世界主要橄榄栽培区的重要病害，由 *Venturia oleaginea*（异名 *Spilocaea oleagina* 和 *Fusicladium oleagineum*）引起。该真菌属于子囊菌门（Ascomycota）、格孢菌目（Pleosporales）、黑星菌科（Venturiaceae）、黑星菌属（*Venturia*）。该菌首次在法国报道（Castagne, 1845），是活体营养型的病原菌，可致橄榄树早期落叶，生长不良并严重减产。但是，该菌的分离需要长达6个月的时间以得到纯的分离物，加上在人工培养条件无法诱导分生孢子产生，阻碍了对该菌开展生物学和分子水平系统性的研究。

为此，我们提出了两步分离方法，该方法利用我们改良的油橄榄叶提取物-Czapek 培养基（OLCZ1:1）分离病原菌，分离纯培养物的成功率可达48%，分离时间显著地缩短到约为两个月。进而，我们将分离的菌株在松针培养基上培养并在紫外光照射下，成功诱导其产生分生孢子；接着，利用人工诱导的分生孢子首次成功地接种橄榄幼苗得到典型的症状。

同时，我们还首次用三代测序的方法，测定获得了采自云南油橄榄园的分离株 YUN35 的高度连续的全基因组序列（46.08 Mb），将基因组组装成61个重叠群，N50为1.80 Mb，最大重叠群长度为2.54 Mb，平均重叠群长度为0.76 Mb，共预测了11540个基因，其中9516个有pfam等功能注释，包括了582个分泌蛋白，有16个DNA片段组装到染色体水平。还发现了次级代谢基因簇，分布于不同基因组 contig 内的13个区域，并与黑星菌属其他成员进行了比较分析。

为了解该菌的系统发育关系，基于 LSU、SSU、ITS、18S 和 EF (TEF1) 等多靶标基因序列进行了系统发育研究。结果显示，不同国家间的 *V. oleaginea* 具有高度相似性，其 SSU、LSU、EF、ITS 和 18S 相似性百分比分别为 99.9%、99.15%、97.97%、99.8%、99.32%。主成分分析 (PCA) 将 *V. oleaginea* 菌株进行了聚类，彼此遗传距离接近，表明其可能有密切的亲缘关系，有共同的祖先。

这项研究通过介绍一种分离和培养 *V. oleaginea* 的方法、展示人工培养基上该真菌菌落的一些特征、揭示最接近物种之间的遗传关系以及介绍诱导病原菌产孢和侵染宿主植物的方法来指导感兴趣的研究人员。所描述的基因组序列和注释资源将有助于研究该真菌的生物学、病原菌与宿主的相互作用、感兴趣的基因特征以及种群遗传多样性。

关键词： 又称叶痂病；菌株分离；产孢诱导；基因组；*Venturia oleaginea*

Abstract

Olive leaf scab, also known as peacock spot disease caused by *Venturia oleagina* (syn. *Spilocaea oleagina* and *Fusicladium oleagineum*) is the main pathogenic fungus attacking olive trees in major cultivation areas around the world. The causal agent *Venturia oleagina* is a pathogenic fungus belonging to the phylum Ascomycota, Pleosporales, Venturiaceae, *Venturia*. The fungus was reported for the first time in France (Castagne 1845). The pathogen has a biotrophic mode of nutrition and causes early defoliation of olive trees, leading to poor growth and fruit yield reduction. One of the main problems preventing interested researchers from working intensely on this pathogen is the isolation process that takes a long time to reach six months to get the pure isolates.

Another problem is the inability of the fungus isolates to produce conidia which are considered as the main inoculum source to infect the host plant. Thus, the published papers that studied the fungus at the molecular level are few.

For the reasons above, in this study, we proposed a double-step isolation protocol to isolate the pathogen using our innovative medium: olive leaves extraction-Czapek media (OLCZ1:1), with a good percentage of pure isolates obtained, reaching 48% from the total prepared isolates, and decreased the isolation time from six months to about two months. We induced the isolated fungus strains to produce conidia by culturing them in pine needles-based media under UV radiation and conducted the first successful olive infection with artificially produced conidia.

Also, we reported the first highly contiguous whole genome sequence (46.08 Mb) of one isolate YUN35 of *V. oleaginea*. The sequenced genome assembled into 61 contigs with N50 of 1.80 Mb, maximum contig length of 2.54 Mb, average

contig length of 0.76 Mb, 11540 genes in total, annotated 9516, and 582 secreted genes, and at least 16 chromosome-size genome was assembled. The secondary metabolic gene clusters were also identified and located in 13 regions within different genome contigs and compared to other *Venturia* members.

The conducted phylogenetic study based on multi-gene regions (LSU, SSU, ITS, 18S, and EF (TEF1)) revealed high similarities with *V. oleaginea* species from different countries. Percentage of identity between *V. oleaginea* were 99.9%, 99.15%, 97.97%, 99.8%, 99.32% % in SSU, LSU, EF, ITS, and 18S, respectively. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) clustered the *V. oleaginea* strains close to each other (one genetic cloud), indicating common ancestry and relatedness to the same genetic pool.

This study will guide the interested researchers by introducing a good method to isolate and cultivate the fungus, exhibit some features of the fungus colonies that grow in artificial media, and show the genetic relations between the closest *Venturia* species, and introduce the method to induce pathogen conidiation to infect the host plant. The described genome sequence and annotation resource will be useful to study the fungal biology, pathogen-host interaction, characterization of genes of interest, and population genetic diversity.

Keywords: Olive leaf scab; pure fungal isolation; conidiation induction; genome, *Venturia oleaginea*.

Chapter 1 Introduction and literature review

1.1 Olive production and importance of olive worldwide

Olive, *Olea europaea* L. is one of the oldest known cultivated plants for human civilization in the Mediterranean region, shaping both the culture and the Mediterranean basin landscape for thousands of years [1,2].

In 2019 more than 10.5 million hectares were planted with olive trees, which is more than the amount of devoted land of apples, bananas, grapes, or mangoes. Only coconut trees and oil palms command more space (Figure 1-1). Cultivation areas quadruple from 2,600,000 to 10.578,561 hectares between 1960 and 2019. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization, the ten largest producing countries are located in the Mediterranean region and produce about 95% of the world's olives and olive oil (Table 1-1).

Figure1- 1 Fruit cultivated area- global level -FAOSTAT (2020).

图 1-1 水果种植面积-全球水平-FAOSTAT (2020 年)。

Available at <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#home> (accessed on 14 January 2021).

Table 1-1 The Production, area, and yield of olive in the largest producing countries in the world. FAOSTAT (2021).

表 1-1 世界上最大的橄榄生产国的产量、面积和产量-FAOSTAT (2021 年)。

Rank	Country\Region	Production (tons)	Cultivated area (hectares)	Yield (q/ha)
1	Spain	5,965,080	2,601,900	22,926
2	Italy	2,194,110	1,139,470	19,256
4	Turkey	1,912,238	879,177	17,346
3	Greece	1,525,000	903,080	13,599
5	Morocco	1,228,130	1,073,493	17,813
6	Egypt	1,080,091	89,942	120,088
7	Portugal	977,040	359,950	27,699
8	Tunisia	876,866	1,606,909	5,457
9	Algeria	868,754	431,634	20,127
10	Syria	844,316	693,227	12,180
—	World	19,467,119	10,578,561	1,247,856

Available at <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#home> (accessed on 14 January 2021).

1.2 Olive description and habitat

The olives are evergreen shrubs or trees that can reach a height of 15-20 m with a too-long life of several hundred to thousands of years in sometimes ^[3]. The tree's botanical name is (*Olea europaea* L.), meaning the European olive and it's kind of small tree belonging to the Oleaceae family, oleideae subfamily subgenus *Olea*. This family includes numerous subspecies with different morphological traits and geographical origins, united by the fact that most of the varieties are self-incompatible and vegetatively propagated. Of the six subspecies that have been described, two show a wide distribution: subsp. European, present in the countries of the Mediterranean basin, and the subsp. *cuspidata*, which spread from Australia ^[4, 5] and is mainly present in Eastern Asia, the Middle East, and southern and eastern Africa. These taxa are diploid, allogamic and anemophilous; their seeds are dispersed through mammals (over short distances) and birds (over long distances) ^[1]. Commercial olives are produced by subsp. European, in fact, only this species produces edible fruits for humans. For the cultivated olive tree, it is believed that, since the beginning of its domestication, the main vector has been man, making it difficult to be able to trace clear diffusion paths ^[6, 7]. The European subspecies is of great economic importance in the Mediterranean, where around 95% of world olive oil production is concentrated (Figure 2-1) while cuspidated subspecies have no significant economic importance.

Olive adapts to the Mediterranean climate with dry and hot summer and cold and wet winter. Olive trees develop well in shallow soils and sloping lands unsuitable for irrigation or annual crops and tolerant to drought conditions [8].

Figure 1-2 olive production worldwide (A)Olive groves in Spain- Andalusia (B) Ancient olive tree in Palestine- Bethlehem (C) Olive production world map (D) Olive oil production market size of different countries. Photos are web sources, map (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QC/visualize>) edited by the author. Pie chart (author).

图 1-2 (西班牙安达卢西亚的橄榄树林 (B) 巴勒斯坦伯利恒的古橄榄树 (C) 世界橄榄生产地图 (D) 不同国家橄榄油生产市场规模。

1.3 Olive's situation in China

Early development of olive cultivation tracked to eastern Mediterranean cost sides origins: Syria, Turkey, Lebanon, Palestine, and Isreal [9], and later olive cultivation shaped all the Mediterranean basin; furthermore, the majority of global cultivation has taken place in that region [1]. Later, Olive cultivation spread to many areas and exists in 40 countries worldwide,

including China (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QC>)^[10]. Domestication of olive to Chinese farms for commercial goals back to 1964, as an experiment to examine some imported olive cultivars' ability to adapt to Chinese climate conditions, before olive was used as an ornamental plant. In 1979 other new varieties were imported and distributed among 12 Provinces and lead to the real establishment of the Olive industry in China^[11-13] (Figure 1-3). Chinese olive growing areas were classified into two levels and six suitable belts for olive cultivation (Table 1-2).

Figure 1-3 China olive regional distribution. 12 provinces are shown on the map where preliminary experiments were conducted in 1979, and these provinces were identified as suitable for olive cultivation. The numbers in this figure correspond to (Table 1-2) for the description of cultivation areas^[12].

图 1-3 中国橄榄区域分布。地图上显示了 1979 年进行初步试验的 12 个省份，这些省份被确定为适合种植橄榄的地区。该图中的数字编号与(表 1-2)中关于种植地区的描述相对应^[12]。

Table 1-2 Olive growing zones in China ^[12].
表1-2 中国的橄榄种植区^[12]。

Level	province	No.	Major Cities
1st	Gansu	1	Wudu, Wenxian, Daixian, Kangxian, Zhouqu
	Yunnan	2	Yongren, Lijiang, Daju, Yongsheng, Binchuan, Ershan
	Sichuan	3	Xichang, Guangyuan, Qingchuan, Santai, Kaijiang
2nd	Sichuan	3	Jintang, Renshou, Mianyang, Langzhong, Luzhou, Bazhong
	Shaanxi	4	Chenggu, Shannan, Hanzhong, Ankang
	Hubei	5	Wuhan, Yichang, Shiyan, Badong
	Chongqing	3	Fengjie, Hechuan, Wanzhou, Wushan
	Yunnan	2	Kunming, Diqing, Ninglang
Common	6. Guizhou (Dushan, Bijie, Duyun) 7. Guangxi (Liuzhou) 8. Hunan (Hengnan, Changsha) 9. Jiangxi (Nanchang) 10. Fujian (Minhou) 11. Zhejiang (Wenzhou, Jinhua) 12. Jiangsu (Nanjing)		

The cultivation area of olive is dramatically increasing in the provinces that were found to be suitable for olive cultivation; for example, olive cultivation area had doubled from 32,200 to 66,400 ha between 2010- 2016. After decades of development, more than 5 million olive trees with annual production reach more than 150,000 kg ^[14]. At the same time, the consumption rate of olive oil in China is increasing, and it's the highest in compared to other consumer countries with 60- 70% yearly, the domestic production of olive oil in China was almost nine times lower than its total olive oil consumption in 2016-2017 ^[12]. According to China's general administration of customs, the imported olive oil in 2000 was 392 tons and in 2016 reached 38636 tons (Figure 1-4).

Figure 1-4 China records of imported, consumption, and production of olive oil

图1-4 中国橄榄油的进口、消费和生产记录.

(Data source available at: <https://daxueconsulting.com/the-olive-oil-industry-in-china/>. (accessed on 28 January 2021)).

This massive demand increasing led to high-planned governmental investments and cultivation area expected to reach 193,400 ha by 2030; consequently, China expected to rank high among the olive producing countries, surpassing some of notable producers countries ^[12] (Table 1-3).

Table 1-3 Cultivation areas in dominant provinces in olive production in China, *Government plan ^[12].

表 1-3 中国油橄榄生产主要省份种植面积, *政府计划 ^[12].

Dominant province	Cultivated Area (10 ⁴ ha)				
	2010	2012	2014	2016	2030
Gansu	1.42	2.00	2.92	3.67	6.67*
Sichuan + Chongqing	1.71	2.15	1.93	2.30	8.00*
Yunnan	0.09	0.16	0.53	0.67	4.67*
Total	3.22	4.38	5.38	6.64	19.34*

1.4 Olive tree pests and diseases

Many pests and diseases can attack olive trees and affect their health, yield, and oil quality [15]. Over 225 organisms were recorded as potentially harmful to the olive trees, and the number is increasing with the identification of new ones; about half of these are animal pests, insects, and plants that can cause damage to the olive tree, while the rest are micro-organisms including viruses, bacteria, and fungi [16, 17].

However, only a small number of these pests and diseases are capable of causing significant importance damage to the olive tree [16]; among these diseases, the fungal disease olive leaf spot caused by *Venturia oleaginea*, which is the most common disease in olive cultivation areas worldwide and caused high losses [18], this fungus will be our topic in this study due to the high losses that this pathogen cause and other various reasons will be discussed in detail later. Also, fungal disease verticillium wilt caused by *Verticillium dahlia* and causes wilting of olive trees, dry twigs, defoliation and, death of seedlings [19], sooty mould is a complex of dark-pigmented caused by secondary infection of fungi of several genera (e.g., *Capnodium*, *Cladosporium*, and *Fumago*), and this complex covers both leaf surfaces and small branches, this coverage causes a shortage in the photosynthesis process and consequently affect normal metabolism leading to weak plant and growth ultimately [20]. From the bacterial side, the bacterium "*Pseudomonas savastanoi*" or olive knot disease, which produce tubercules forms on the branches and stems causes [21].

Furthermore, numerous pests, which generally cause serious damage to olive trees; insects like olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*) is considered the most damaging insect pest attacking olive fruits and causes severe economic damage to olive production, affecting oil extraction and oil quality [22], olive moth (*Prays oleae*, synonym: *Prays oleellus*) and attacking olive fruits, black scale (*Saissetia oleae*) colonized at olive branches, Jasmin moth (*Palpita vitrealis*) attacks young shoots flowers, bark beetles (*Hylesinus oleiperda* and *Phloeotribus scarabaeoides*) causing branches and trunk damage, psyllids (*Euphyllura olivina*) sucking on flowers, mites (*Aceria oleae*) on leaves and fruits, and thrips (*Liothrips oleae*) on flowers and young leaves [16, 23-25].

1.5 Olive leaf scab (OLS)

1.5.1 Olive leaf scab causal agent

The olive leaf scab's causal agent is the pathogenic fungi *Venturia oleagineae* (Castagne) Rossman & Crous (synonyms *Spilocaea oleagina* (castagne) S. Hughes and *Fusicladium oleagineum* (Castagne) Ritschel & U. Braun). The disease also has different common names like olive peacock spot and olive leaf spot. The pathogen was reported for the first time in France [26]. The fungus is a deuteromycete fungal plant belonging to the phylum Ascomycota, Pleosporales, Venturiaceae, *Venturia* (Figure 1-5).

Figure 1-5 *Venturia oleaginea* Taxonomy.

图 1- 5 *Venturia oleagineae* 的分类。

Olive is the only known potential host of the pathogen, and all olive cultivars can be infected; however, different cultivars vary in their susceptibility [27].

1.5.2 Olive leaf scab symptoms & economic importance

Symptoms are mainly confined to leaves on the upper surface and appear like dark brown, circular, zonate spots; the spots turn dark brown and become necrotic and surrounded by yellow haloes (2-15 mm) size in diameter with age. In severe infection, the fungus can attack leaf stalk, fruit stem, and fruit [28]. Fungus shows a typical subcuticular growth, forming flat colonies within the thick epidermal cell wall's cutinized layer [18] and cause tree weakness and high defoliation[29].

Figure 1-6 Olive leaf scab (*Venturia oleaginea*) symptoms.

图1-6 橄榄叶斑病 (*Venturia oleaginea*) 症状。

Conidia, which formed at the apex of short ampulliform conidiophores, are the only parts responsible for the infection process [30]. Rain droplets usually carry conidia, but recent data show that humid air currents and insects also contribute to limited aerial dissemination [27, 31].

The disease causes severe defoliation in the olive trees, and sometimes it leads to the branches' death. In areas with rainy winters, the infected trees which not treated with identified fungicides for this disease can lose half of their leaves [18, 32].

In 1998, the defoliation incidence in olive trees reached more than 80% in the Mirandela region in Portugal [33]; this early defoliation greatly affects the differentiated flower buds, and thus the later fruit-bearing and severe infection with olive leaf scab disease lead to the fruit's failure to develop and fruits fall [34], in 1993, the losses caused by disease in Turkey were about 20%. Also, high losses were reported in Cordoba – Spain 1998 season [35]. In New Zealand found that 40% of trees have leaf scab disease, which plays a significant role in low productivity due to

severe defoliation and sometimes leads to the death of new branches; consequently, production decreases in the following year [27, 28, 36]. in oily cultivars, OLS infection leads to delayed ripening and reduced quantity and quality of the oil and also can cause unfavorable discoloration in table olive varieties [18].

1.5.3 Distribution and favourable conditions:

The disease exists in all olive production areas: the Mediterranean basin, South Africa, California, South America, Australia, and Asian production countries (Figure1-7). However, its distribution in olive groves is not uniform and determined by cultivar sensitivity as indicated and the environmental conditions, particularly humid climate with cool winter temperatures [37].

Figure 1-7 *Venturia oleaginea* incidents linked to olive growing areas worldwide.

图 1-7 *Venturia oleaginea* 的存在与全世界橄榄种植区有关。

The fungus typically develops within between 10- 20°C temperature limits; areas with rainy winters, temperate spring, and long autumn are subjected to heavy infection by this pathogen. Areas with high humidity, like groves near rivers, ponds, nurseries, and dense farms with poor ventilation, also can be severely infected [27, 37, 38].

1.5.4 Infection with OLS and disease cycle

Despite the large losses due to the OLS disease in most olive growing areas, little information is known about this pathogen's biology [29]. The pathogen can generally survive in unfavorable conditions, e.g., dry, hot weather, fallen leaves, and infected leaves on the tree. The conidia formed in leaves on the tree can survive for several months; however, once they have separated from the conidiophores, they lose their germination ability in less than a week. Fallen infected leaves on the ground and, as well as those that remained on the tree, are the source of inoculum for the current season or allow the fungus to stay over winter and inoculate the healthy leaves in the next season [39].

The fungus is colonized between the cuticle and the inner cuticular layer of the epidermal cell wall, forming flat radial colonies [18], and this happens when the infection hyphae penetrate the leaves by piercing and degrading the cuticle layer with the help of cutinase enzyme and remain localized in a cutinized layer until the leaf tissues decay. Later hyphae in decayed tissue emerging to spread at the leaf surface and produce conidiophores and conidia, which is the source of infection and subsequent infection [40].

Infection with OLS can occur at any time of the year when the proper infection conditions are available, mainly high humidity, low temperatures and low light intensity. Conidia needs low temperatures to germinate with a range between 5 °C -25 °C and 15 °C is the optimum temperature for germ tube elongation. Conidia germination's main factors are high humidity > 98%, and the wetting period extends to about 48 hours. The percentage of germinating conidia decreases linearly in proportion to leaf age, being 58% at two weeks and 35% at ten weeks leaf age. Formation of appressoria occurred six h after the first signs of germination. However, no conidia germination or appressoria formation without the wetting period, even with optimum temperatures and optimum RH%. Often OLS infection and development peak between late autumn to spring and low incidence between early July to middle of November [27, 41, 42].

Latent infection before appearing of OLS symptoms depends on several factors, including olive cultivar, environmental conditions, seasonal tree growth, leaf age, and agricultural practices like fungicides and fertilizers. Susceptibility of olive trees to OLS was affected by its nutritional status, e.g., soil deficient in calcium and excessive nitrogen fertilizers increase the tree's susceptibility to OLS infection [29, 43, 44]. Salerno (1966) determined the

incubation period under the optimum temperature below 20 °C as 15 days in Italy. Anyway, this period may last for several weeks or even months or may stay latent over the same season if the infection is followed by hot or dry periods, and symptoms appear when appropriate conditions for the disease development are available [29, 45]. The following figure is the proposed life cycle of the OLS.

Figure 1-8 Proposed life cycle of *Venturia oleaginea* [29]
图 1-8 拟议的 *Venturia oleaginea* 生活史. [29]

1.5.5 Olive leaf scab management

Despite the fact is the pathogen can attack most known olive cultivars but choosing the resistant olive cultivars is the main key in OLS management since olive cultivars show differing susceptibilities to OLS [46-48]. Accordingly, improving susceptible cultivars through the selection and breeding programs using molecular tools and deeper studies in molecular plant-pathogen interaction should be useful in breeding programs.

Few *in-vitro* studies have been conducted to use alternative control methods to apply the chemicals, particularly using bacterial bacillus strains to inhibit fungal conidia germination [49, 50].

Despite the promising results in inhibition conidia germination with more than 90% in some conducted experiments, however, there are still no field trials that have proven successful in controlling the disease, and further investigations are required to evaluate the efficacy of the bacteria under field conditions.

Chemicals application is the most widely used method to control the disease in addition to some agricultural practices like pruning, choosing resistant cultivars, and fertilizing [45, 50]. Control of OLS is mainly based on copper applications. Successful control only occurred at low disease levels and integrated with good timing prior to winter rains to use these applications [18, 51]. Many studies have been published regarding olive varieties' resistance/susceptibility to infection with olive leaf scab [52-54]. In 2019, a phenotypic profile of varieties (resistant/susceptible) related to the olive leaf spot (*V.oleagineae*) fungus was published for the public through BeFOre project (Table 1-4), Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5c2b5a609&appId=PPGMS> (Accessed on 1 February 2021).

Table 1-4 Phenotypic profile of varieties (resistant/ susceptible) related to the olive leaf spot.

表 1-4 不同橄榄品种的叶斑病(抗性/感性)表型概况。

Cultivar	Phenotypic profile varieties (lowly / highly susceptible) related to the OLS	Cultivar	Phenotypic profile varieties (lowly / highly susceptible) related to the OLS
Arbequina	medium -highly susceptible	Manzanilla	medium -highly susceptible
Ascolana semitenera	medium susceptible	Manzanilla carresquena	medium -highly susceptible
Ascolana tenera	medium susceptible	Maurino	medium susceptible
Bella di Cerignola	medium -highly susceptible	Mignola	medium susceptible
Canino	medium susceptible	Moraiolo	highly susceptible
Carolea	highly susceptible	Morchiaio	highly susceptible
Casaliva	highly susceptible	Moresca	highly susceptible
Cima di Mola	medium susceptible	Nostrale di Rigali	medium -highly susceptible
Cipressino	medium susceptible	Ogliarola di Bitonto	medium -highly susceptible
Coratina	medium -highly susceptible	Ogliarola Salentina	highly susceptible

Isolation, biological characterization and genome sequencing of *Venturia oleaginea*, the causal agent of olive leaf scab

Cornicabra	highly susceptible	Olivago Sabino	lowly susceptible
Corniolo	medium -highly susceptible	Orbetana	medium susceptible
Cucca	medium susceptible	Ottobratica	medium susceptible
Dolce Agogia	medium susceptible	Pendolino	medium -highly susceptible
Dritta di Loreto	medium -highly susceptible	Piangente	medium susceptible
Dritta di Moscufo	medium -highly susceptible	Picholine De Languedoc	medium susceptible
Fecciario	highly susceptible	Picholine Marocaine	highly susceptible
Frantoio	medium -highly susceptible	Picual	highly susceptible
Gentile di Chieti	medium -highly susceptible	Rastrellina	medium -highly susceptible
Giarraffa	highly susceptible	Raza	highly susceptible
Gordal Sevillana	medium susceptible	Razzola	medium susceptible
Gordales	medium susceptible	Rosciola	medium susceptible
Grossa di Spagna	highly susceptible	San Felice	medium -highly susceptible
Grossanne	medium -highly susceptible	Sant' Agostino	medium susceptible
Hojiblanca	highly susceptible	Santa Caterina	medium -highly susceptible
Itrana	medium susceptible	Santagatese	medium -highly susceptible
Kalamata	medium -highly susceptible	Sargano	medium -highly susceptible
Konservolia	highly susceptible	Sorani	medium susceptible
Koroneiki	lowly susceptible	Taggiasca	medium -highly susceptible
Laurina	medium -highly susceptible	Tanche	highly susceptible
Leccino	lowly susceptible	Uovo di Piccione	medium susceptible
Leccio del corno	lowly susceptible	Verdale	highly susceptible
Lechin de Sevilla	medium -highly susceptible	Chemlaly	Susceptible ^[53]
Souri	highly susceptible ^[54]	Misson	medium susceptible ^[54]
Mv97/3	highly susceptible ^[54]	Meski	medium susceptible ^[54]
Haas	highly susceptible ^[54]	Arbosana	Very low susceptible ^[54]

1.5.6 Isolation methods of *V. oleaginea* & *in-vitro* host plant infection

There is no standard protocol to isolate the fungus; interested researchers used various methods to get the pure isolates. The time to get the fungus in artificial media also varies from one month reaching six months in some studies [55-57]. The table below shows the main isolation methods and media used to isolate the fungus (Table 1-5).

Table 1-5 Comparison of olive leaf scab pathogen isolation methods
表 1-5 不同橄榄叶痂病病原菌分离方法的比较

Isolation method	Media used	Time to get the pure isolate and DNA extraction	Number of obtained isolates	References
Single spore isolation	Olive leaves extract (OLE) enriched with PDA.	3-6 months	92	[29]
	(OLE) + PDA (potato dextrose agar).	3 months	52	[58]
	Czapek media	3 months	6	[59]
	Special OLE agar media (no preparation method)	2 months	1	[60]
Isolation from Plant tissue (leaves)	Liquid Potato dextrose	One month	1	[57]

As indicated, the conidia are the main source to infect the host plants. Isolates grown in artificial media are unable to produce conidia. As far we knew, all the previous experiments have been conducted to study the fungus infection process like conidia germination, plant tissue penetration, appressorial formation, etc., used the infected leaves as a natural source of conidia to infect the plant.[27, 61, 62].

Summary and objectives

By reviewing the published papers in English language or other languages that can be accessed related to OLS epidemiology studies, several facts about the pathogen can be summarized as the following:

- 1- The pathogen *V. oleaginea* is very hard to get in artificial media and not easy to isolate, and it needs a long time to get small amounts of mycelia.
- 2- Most researchers reported that the obtained isolates in artificial media are unable to produce conidia. Thus infection of the plant using conidia produced in artificial media is still inapplicable on *V. oleaginea*.
- 3- Due to the previous facts, work at the molecular level on this pathogen still very poor. The previous works were mostly genetic diversity studies, gene cloning, and susceptible cultivars screening using molecular primers and phylogenetic studies based on one *V. oleaginea* isolate [56-58, 60, 63].

The main goal of this study is to get more knowledge and understanding of *Venturia oleaginea* by:

- 1- Proposing a useful protocol to isolate the pathogen (proper isolation and growing media).
- 2- Try to induce pathogen sporulation in artificial media and infect the host plant.
- 3- To set the first draft genome of the pathogen.
- 4- Conduct a comprehensive phylogenetic study for the pathogen from the obtained isolates and get more knowledge about the venturiaceae family phylogenetic and evolutionary relations.

Chapter 2 Isolation, identification, and sporulation induction of *Venturia oleaginea*, the causal agent of olive leaf scab

2.1 Introduction

Venturia oleaginea (syn: *spilocaea oleagina* [26]) is the main pathogenic fungus attacking olive trees in cultivation areas around the world and causes yield losses reaching up to 20% [27]. Leaves are the parts of the plant customarily infected, and in severe cases, the pathogen also attacks stalks and fruits. The pathogen causes dark-colored circular spots, which are sometimes surrounded by a yellowish halo developed in the leaves' upper part, and diffused spots may appear on the leaf underside along the central vein [64]. Like most other *Venturia* species, no ascocarps were found yet in nature, for *V. oleaginea*; conidia are only the parts responsible for the infection process [30], and infection will happen in case the existence of favorable conditions for conidia to develop like: rain, wind, and insects to spread the spores, long wet period and low temperature for germination and leaves penetration, high humidity with low temperature for fungus development and vitality after penetration [27, 31].

Getting pure isolates of *V. oleaginea* is a little bit-hard mission since the fungus takes a long time to grow into a visible colony [55]. The single spore isolation method is often used to obtain pure isolates of *V. oleaginea* [55, 56]. PDA, Czapek, and olive leaves extract agar media were the major media used to isolate the pathogen with various isolations periods to get the pure strains. The inability to produce conidia is another distinguishing feature of *V. oleaginea* strains obtained *in vitro* [27]. Thus, morphological identification of *V. oleaginea* is a little tricky due to missing the asexual reproduction parts, which are essential taxa. Therefore, molecular identification is a useful method to identify this fungus.

Working at the molecular level on *V. oleaginea* is still very poor; just a few papers were published before and were mostly related to genetic variation and phylogeny analysis [56, 58, 60, 63]. According to González-Lamothe, Segura, Trapero, Baldoni, Botella, and Valpuesta [60], *S. oleaginea* is an anamorphic phase of a yet unidentified *Venturia* species; recently, the full genome sequence of one strain Y35 was published by us [65].

Previous inoculation experiments aimed at infecting the host plant were conducted using conidia obtained from nature. Thus, mycologist's criteria (Koch's postulates) used for defining the relationship between any microbe and potential host are inapplicable on *V. oleaginea*. The reasons why *V. oleaginea* strains obtained *in-vitro* are unable to produce conidia are still unknown, and they may need an inducer to produce conidia and infect the host plant. Several studies have been conducted to study the conidia germination and best infection conditions using conidia obtained from infected leaves to infect the healthy ones. [27, 61, 62], and as far as we know, the host plant's infection using strains isolated in artificial media has not succeeded yet with *V. oleaginea*.

Some plant tissues can induce sporulation in many fungi species [66]; for example, pine needles were added to agar media to induce pycnidia production in some *Botryosphaeriaceae* spp. [67]. Carnation is a suitable enhancer for sporulation in *Fusarium* and *Pestalotiopsis* species [68-70]. Branch segments of *Sophora japonica* generate sporulation of the endophytic fungi from lichens [71]. *Gardeniawere* or *Hydrangea* leaves can induce perithecia and ascospore production in *Glomerella cingulata*, *Mycosphaerella allicina*, *Guignardia sp*, *Metasphaeria sp.*, and *Pleospora herbarum* [72]. Yoshida and Shirata [73] examined the leaves of 22 plant species to induce sporulation of *Colletotrichum dematium*, and they found that organic compounds like biotin in mulberry leaves play some role in sporulation in the same species.

In addition to plant tissues, there are some other techniques that can be used to enhance the sporulation; for example, Luchi, Bonello and Capretti [74] studied the nutrition, host tissue, and light effect on sporulation behavior for numbers of examined fungi in artificial media, and induced the production of pycnidia of *Diplodia scrobiculata* and *D. pinea*, the two species are recalcitrant to sporulation in pure culture. Pulz and Massola Jr [75] found that near UV light, colonies scratching, and 12 h light / 12 h dark photoperiod can induce sporulation in *Alternaria dauci*. Furthermore, oleic acid can induce the vegetative-conidial germination, and media that contains both Casamino acids and oleic acid can help in second sporulation in *Entornophthora culicis* [76]. There are many ways to induce sporulation in many fungi species, and some of these techniques are worth trying with *V. oleaginea* to enhance the fungus to produce the conidia.

This study's overall goals are to find the proper isolation method, get more knowledge in morphological identification, and infect the plant using conidia produced in artificial media and move forward in studying fungus-host relation.

2.2 Materials and methods

2.2.1 Plant and fungal materials

During May-June/2018-2017, infected olive leaves from different cultivars with clear symptoms were collected from three provinces of China: Yunnan, Sichuan, Gansu, and infected olive leaves from Palestine (a Mediterranean country). Leaves were placed in envelopes and let dry at room temperature for 3 days, then stored at 4°C until required for isolation. (Table 2-1).

Table 2-1 *Venturia oleaginea* obtained isolates, geographic information.

表 2-1 获得的 *Venturia oleaginea* 分离株的地理信息。

No.	Sample site	Obtained isolates names & olive tree cultivar	No. of isolates	Coordinates
1	Tulkarem, West Bank - Palestine	TL1, TL2, TL3, TL5 (Nabali)	4	N 31°40' 48" E 35° 09' 20"
2	Ramallah, West Bank- Palestine	P2,P3,P4,P5(Nabali)/ P3M,P1 (Nabali Mohassan)	6	N 31°59' 32" E 35°06' 54"
3	Bethlehem, West Bank- Palestine	P,P11, P17, P18, P20 (Nabali)/ P19 (Surri)	6	N 31°41' 34" E 35°05' 14"
4	Qalqilya, West Bank- Palestine	P6, P7, P16, P9 (Nabali)	4	N 32°13' 17" E 35° 8' 20"
5	China, Liangshan -Sichuan (two sites)	X3 (Coratina)/ X8,X7, X50, X49 (unknown)/ X46 (Koroneiki)/ X48, X10 (Picholine)/ X13 (Barnea)/ X14 (Frantoio)	10	N 27° 44' 27" E 102°14' 01" N 28° 21' 12" E 102°09' 41"
6	China, Kunming, Yongren-Yunnan (Three sites)	Y1 (Coratina)/ Y24,Y3,Y6,Y48 (Picholine)/ Y19,Y20 (Tanche)/ Y22,Y30, Y31,Y33 (Leccino)/ Y26,Y29 (Frantoio)/ Y5 (unknown)/Y2 (Manzanilla)/ Y21, Y35 (Pecual)/ Y41,Y23 (E'ZhiNo.8)/ Y14 (Manzanilla)/Y28 (Ascolano)	21	N 25° 08' 47" E 102°44' 47" N 25°58' 02" E 101° 42' 43" N 26° 01' 20" E 101°38' 33"
7	China, Longnan & Liangshui Gansu	L5, L6, L8, L11(unknown)/ L3 ,L2 L9,LS89 (E'ZhiNo.8)/ LS117 (Manzanilla)/ LS80 (Barnea)/ LS94, L4 Picholine)/ L1,L23,L7 (Coratina)/ L21 (Arbequina)/ L22 (Koroneiki)/ L12 (keji)/ LS20,L27 (Leccino)	20	N 33° 20' 16" E 105° 00' 20" N 33° 26' 13" E 104° 48' 04"
8	China, Muyuzhen-Qingchuan Sichuan	M55,M46,M10 (Frantoio)/ M24, M53,M57,M49,M40 (Picholine)/ M56,M43 (Arbequina)/ M2,M58 (unknown)/ M1,M7 (Cheng'Gu no.32)/ M22 E'(ZhiNo.8)/ M47 (Leccino)/ M3 (Coratina)	17	N 32° 39' 37" E 105°30' 18"
Total isolates			88	

2.2.2 Preparation of isolation and growing media

The following media were prepared to isolate the pathogen from the host plant:

1. Potato dextrose agar medium (PDA, GuangDong Huaki Microbial Sci. And Tech. Co.Ltd.), following manufacturer instructions.
 2. Czapek agar media (CZ) according to *Sigma –Aldrich* protocol (<https://www.sigmaaldrich.com>).
 3. Olive leaves extract media (OL) media, according to ^{*[29]}.
 4. Water agar medium (15g, 1 L water).
 5. Potato dextrose broth medium (PDB, GuangDong Huaki Microbial Sci. And Tech. Co.Ltd.), following the manufacturer instructions.
 6. Mixtures of olive leaves and Czapek media with ratios (2:1, 1:1, 1:2) prepared by mixing the liquid formulas of both media, and then agar was added (1.5g/100ml), mixtures will be expressed later as (OLCZ 2:1), (OLCZ 1:1), and (CZOL 2:1).
- All media were autoclaved at 121°C for 20 min; *Ampicillin antibacterial (100µg/ml) was added to all media upon use.

2.2.3 Preparation of sporulation induction media

The following media were prepared to induce the pathogen for sporulation:

1. Olives leave extract medium (OL) as indicated.
 2. Pine needles medium (PN), according to ^[66], pH. adjusted to 7.
 3. Pine needles media with olive leaves medium. (PNOL1:1), both media prepared in liquid, mixed with 1:1 ratio, and agar 2% added.
 4. PDA (1/10 strength) medium: as stated by ^[66].
 5. A mixture of (Olive leaves media + PDA 1/10 media), both media prepared in liquid and mixed with 1:1 ratio, agar 2% added.
 6. 2%Agar medium as a control.
- For each medium from 1-5, we added these supplements: (oleic acid), (oleic acid + Casamino acid), (oleic acid + Casamino acid + d-biotin) to prepare three sets of each media in addition to the original media (Table 2-2).

- To the control media, we added: (Oleic acid), (oleic acid + Casamino acid + d-biotin) to prepare two sets in addition to the original one (Table 2-2).
- Supplements were added in 0.1 % (w/v) each, oleic acid added after autoclaving just before media solidification, and antibacterial agent ampicillin (100 µg/ml) added to all media upon use and autoclaved all at 121°C for 20 min.

Table 2-2 Media and supplements used to induce sporulation in *Venturia oleaginea*, experimental design.

表 2-2 用于诱导 *Venturia oleaginea* 孢子产生的培养基和补充剂，以及实验重复次数。

Cultural media	Total replicates	Cultural media	Total replicates
1- Olive leaves media (OL)	20	2- (1/10 strength PDA)+OL: (PDAOL)	20
OL+ oleic acid	20	(PDAOL)+ oleic acid	20
OL+ oleic acid+ Casamino acid	20	(PDAOL)+ oleic acid+ Casamino acid	20
OL+ oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin	20	(PDAOL)+ oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin	20
3- Pine needles agar media (PN)	20	4- PN + OL : (PNOL)	20
PN + oleic acid	20	(PNOL) + oleic acid	20
PN + oleic acid+ Casamino acid	20	(PNOL) + oleic acid+ Casamino acid	20
PN + oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin.	20	(PNOL) + oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin.	20
5- (1/10 strength PDA)	20	6- Agar (control)	20
1/10 PDA+ oleic acid	20	Agar + oleic acid+ Casamino acid+Biotin.	20
1/10 PDA + oleic acid+ Casamino acid	20		
1/10 PDA + oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin.	20		

2.2.4 Isolation using the single spore method

Conidial suspension prepared by putting small cuts of lesions in 2 ml Eppendorf tube, 500-1000 µl of double-distilled water (ddH₂O) added, shaking using a pipette for 10-20s, then spread 100 µl of the conidial suspension into Petri dishes containing 4% agar, incubate at 20 °C for 24 hours, conidia with developing germ tube were transferred to new permanent Petri dishes of PDA, olive leaves extract (OL), Czapek (CZ) and olive leaves –Czapek (OLCZ1:1) as indicated, Petri-dishes were sealed and incubated at 20°C adjusted to 12:12 hours of low light intensity and dark period (Figure 2-1).

Figure 2-1 *Venturia oleaginea* conidial solution and spore germination. (A) Conidia suspension 50µm; (B) germinated conidium after 24 hr. in 4% Agar media. Bar, 20µm.

图 2-1 *Venturia oleaginea* 分生孢子液和孢子萌发。(A) 分生孢子悬液 50 µm (B) 在 4% 琼脂培养基中萌发 24 小时后的分生孢子。标尺, 20 µm。

2.2.5 Isolation from plant tissue

Lesions of infected leaves were randomly chosen and cut into (0.5 mm), washed with tap water for several seconds; surface sterilization carried out using: 1- mercuric chlorides 0.1 % for a30s then 70% ethanol 30s, and 2- with ethanol 70% for a30s), sterilized cuts were washed three times with (ddH₂O) to remove the traces of chemicals used and were placed carefully in Petri-plates contains growing media as indicated, then incubated at 20°C, with low light intensity: dark period 12:12 hours.

2.2.6 Morphology and identification

The tentative identification of the isolates was performed based mainly on the morphological characteristics of the colony; shape, color, hyphae growing styles, ability to produce conidia, and advanced knowledge of the slow growth rate of *V. oleaginea* [55, 56]. The obtained isolates were documented, and colonies' texture, color, and hyphae were microscopically examined.

2.2.7 DNA extraction, molecular PCR verification

Genomic DNA from all samples (68 from Chinese, 20 from Palestinian locations) was extracted using the CTAB method by grinding 100-150 mg of mycelium with liquid Nitrogen, then Incubate for about 40 minutes at 65°C in a recirculating water bath with inversion every 10 minutes. After incubation, 500 µl of Chloroform: Iso Amyl Alcohol (24:1) was added to each tube and mixed by inversion. Then the extract mixture was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 6 min. Supernatant around 350µl transferred to clean 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube. Absolute ice-cold ethanol (800 µl) added, then slowly inverting the tubes several times to precipitate the DNA. The extract mixture was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 6 min. after centrifuging, the supernatant was discarded. DNA washed twice by adding 800 µl of ice-cold 70 % ethanol, slowly inverting the tube, and then centrifuged at 12500 rpm for 5 minutes, in first washing to form a pellet, let dry, and finally obtained pellet of DNA dissolved in sterile DNase free water (approximately 80 µl H₂O; contains 10 µl of RNase).

2.2.8 PCR amplification of fungal rDNA

Molecular identification was carried out using PCR based specific primers; internal transcribed spacer (ITS) amplified with primers ITS4 and ITS5, partial small subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (SSU) region amplified with primers NS1 and NS4^[77], and partial larger subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (LSU) region amplified with LROR and LR5^[78].

A. DNA cloning with partial small subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (SSU)

Genomic DNA samples of *V. oleaginea* were used for PCR amplification using primers NS1 (GTAGTCATATGCTTGTCTC) and NS4 (CTTCCGTCAATTCCTTTAAG). PCR reagents were A4 fidelity (1.1X) PCR mix (Gimmico Biotech Co., Ltd), components concentrations according to manufacturer's instructions, and PCR thermal cycles adjusted as shown in (Table 2-3).

Table 2-3 PCR components concentrations and PCR program set for amplifying *Venturia oleaginea* genomic DNA with (small-subunit 18S RNA) primers.

表 2-3 用 (小亚基 18S RNA) 引物扩增 *Venturia oleaginea* 基因组 DNA 的 PCR 成分浓度和 PCR 程序集。

Components	volume	Final Conc.	PCR /Step	Temp.°C	Time	cycles
PCR mix(1.1X)	45 µl	1X	Initial denaturation	95	5 min	1
10 µM F. primer	2 µl	0.4 µM	Denature	95	40 s	35
10 µM R. primer	2 µl	0.4 µM	Anneal	55	40 s	35
Template	1 µl	≈ 100ng/rxn.	Ext.	72	1 min	35
Total / rxn.	50 µl	Final Conc.	Final Extension	72	10 min	1

Eight µl of the PCR product were separated by running on a 1.5 % Agarose gel (Beijing Solarbio Science & Technology Co.Ltd) in TRIS-acetate-EDTA (40 mM TBE; TRIS-acetate, 1mM EDTA, pH 8.0), stained with ethidium bromide and visualized using Gel Image System Tanon 3500R(Tanon Science & Technology Co., Ltd).

B. DNA cloning with ITS (internal transcribed spacer) region primers

Genomic DNA samples of *V. oleaginea* were used for PCR amplification using ITS4 (TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC) and ITS5 (GGAAGTAAAAGTCGTAACA- AGG) in a 50 µl final reaction volume. PCR Reagents and conditions were the same for 18S rDNA, except for primer annealing temperature, which was 50 °C for 1 min. Gel electrophoresis reagents, gell visualizing conditions, and sequencing were performed the same as for 18s rDNA.

C. DNA cloning with partial larger subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (LSU) region

Primers from the partial larger subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (LSU) region were used to amplify the genomic DNA of *V. oleaginea*, LROR and LR5 sequences were (ACCCGCTGAACTTAAGC), and (ATCCTGAGGGAACTTC) respectively. PCR Reagents and conditions were the same as 18s rDNA. Gel electrophoresis reagents, gell visualizing conditions, and sequencing were the same for 18s rDNA and ITS.

The obtained sequences were edited using SnapGene software (GSL Biotech LLC, Chicago, IL, USA). NCBI's web Blastn tool was used to download the closest species. The obtained sequences of ITS, LSU, and SSU regions were aligned separately with Pro-Coffee Aligns homologous promoter regions web tool [79]. Evolutionary analyses were conducted using MEGA X [80]. Phylogenetic trees were calculated by the neighbor-Joining method [81]. Bootstrap analysis was performed 1000 times to confirm the produced trees' reliability [82], and The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter method [83]. *Fusarium oxysporum* partial sequences of ITS, LSU, and SSU regions (*KF914478.1*, *AY118130.1*, *DQ831923.1*), respectively, were used as out-group in each tree.

2.2.9 Assessment of growth rate of *V. oleaginea* isolates in different media

Small colony discs with (1mm) diameter from 10 randomly chosen isolates were cut and transferred to the 35mm Petri dishes which contained selected media as indicated, measurements taken with weekly intervals and extend to about three months, five replicates prepared for each isolate in each media, at least three replicates included in analyzing to compare growth means in different media.

2.2.10 Assessment of different pH. on colony growth

Two isolates were chosen randomly (TL2- Palestine/M10- China). Discs with (2mm) diameter were cut and inoculated in 35mm Petri dishes containing PDA and olive leaves extract agar media. pH. values were adjusted within the range of (4.5- 9.5). 10 replicates in total for both isolates, and at least eight replicates were included in the analysis to compare the growth rates in different pH.

2.2.11 Stimulate sporulation of *V. oleaginea*

Two isolates were randomly selected from both countries. Mycelial cuts were inoculated in prepared media as indicated. Isolates in media that failed to stimulate the fungus for sporulation were exposed firstly to two weeks of Light/dark 12:12 hrs., combined with temperature fluctuation between 15 °C and 10 °C in light / dark respectively, then to 14 days of

UV light (300-500 nm, 12:12 dark-light duration), and finally to scratching and to check after one week.

2.2.12 Plant inoculation, infection conditions, and Isolate the pathogen from infected plants

In March 2020, nine olive seedlings with different varieties (E-Z8, Pecholine, and Picual-five each) were inoculated with *V. oleaginea* strain (Y41). Inoculated seedlings were placed in an open field at Fujian agriculture and forestry university, Fuzhou, for about one month after inoculation. Later we transferred the infected plants to 20 °C chamber room with about 70% RH. In March, Fuzhou's climate can be summarized as mild and wet, with over 80% RH, mostly cloudy, and an average of 3.5 hours of sunshine per day. Daytime maximum temperatures around 18°C and at night were 10°C, <https://www.weather2visit.com/asia/china/fuzhou-march.htm>. <https://lishi.tianqi.com/fuzhou/202003.html> (accessed April 2020), Previous climate conditions are typically the favorable conditions for *V. oleaginea* to infect the plant [27].

Conidial inoculum with 10⁵/ml concentration was used to inoculate the olive seedlings by placing drops of it on the center of intact and injured leaves of 2 plants, five leaves each. Also, un-sporulated mycelium agar cuts obtained from plates of the same strain cultured in PDA media were used as inoculum and placed on the surface of injured leaves of tree seedlings, five leaves each.

After inoculating the olive seedlings with conidia obtained in-vitro and the plants have shown the known symptoms of olive leaf scab disease (*V. oleaginea*) infection, single spores from the infected leaves were cultured in proposed media and compared with the colonies developed from conidia collected from olive leaves.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Isolation methods and growing media

Isolation with a single spore method showed good results in getting pure isolates, whereas no growth or contaminations occurred during or after six months of the isolation process. The single spore isolation method we used to isolate the fungus in pre-prepared media under the same aseptic conditions gave us an overall percentage of 23.75% of pure isolates

(Supplementary Table S1). The obtained colonies developed well in PDA, OL, and OLCZ1:1 media while grew sparsely in Czapek media. OLCZ 1:1 medium had the highest number of pure isolates obtained with 48% from all prepared with this method. Contamination was the main feature with PDA media, and only 5% pure isolates were obtained after two months (Figure 2-2).

Figure 2-2 Single spore isolation method. (A) *Venturia oleaginea* total pure isolates obtained in single spores isolation method, statistical significance at $P < 0.05$ was determined using one way ANOVA, by comparing the number of obtained isolates vs. different media, Bars represent the Std. Deviation (B) Mono-spore isolate of *Venturia oleaginea* cultured in OLCZ (1:1) / from the left; after 21days, 60days, 90 days, colony back view, a dispersed colony from a single spore.

Figure 2-2 单孢分离法。(A) 单孢分离法获得的 *Venturia oleaginea* 纯分离株，采用单因素方差分析获得的分离株数与不同培养基的比较，以 $P < 0.05$ 为统计学意义，条形代偏差 (B) 在 OLCZ 中培养的 *Venturia oleaginea* 的单孢分离物 (1:1) / 从左边开始，21 天、60 天、90 天后，菌落背视图是来自单孢的菌落图。

Among all media used in this experiment, our results indicated that the OLZC1:1 is the best medium to obtain pure isolates of *V. oleaginea*; however, colony growth is still very slow and consistent with others description for *V. oleaginea* isolation time (Figure 2 B), so another related experiment was conducted to see if we can accelerate the growth rate in Petri-dishes after the isolation process.

2.3.2 Assessment of growth rate of *V. oleaginea* isolates in different media

Thirteen weeks after inoculation of tiny discs of mycelial agar (1mm) obtained from the isolates as indicated, the results showed that PDA, OLCZ 2:1, and OL media had the highest radial growth rates with 12.78 mm, 11.26 mm, and 11.26 mm, respectively. Table (2-4) shows

the *V. oleaginea* radial growth rates in each media used in different weeks of experiment duration.

Table 2-4 Average of *Venturia oleaginea* colonies radial growth in different media.

表 2-4 *Venturia oleaginea* 菌落在不同培养基中生长的平均值。

Time	PDA	Agar	Czapek	CZOL2:1	OLCZ1-1	OLCZ2:1	OL
Initial diameter (mm).	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Week 1	1.74±0.03	1.06±0.01	1.08±0.01	1.19±0.01	1.35±0.02	1.48±0.06	1.83±0.03
Week 2	2.18±0.08	1.16±0.01	1.21±0.02	1.45±0.03	1.63±0.05	1.94±0.08	2.62±0.07
Week 3	2.71±0.12	1.27±0.01	1.37±0.04	1.70±0.05	2.05±0.1	2.36±0.09	3.48±0.09
Week 4	4.32±0.19	2.00±0.10	1.76±0.10	2.29±0.09	3.03±0.22	4.06±0.28	4.38±0.12
Week 5	4.72±0.19	2.05±0.10	1.84±0.12	2.51±0.12	3.45±0.30	4.40±0.33	4.55±0.14
Week 6	5.51±0.16	2.56±0.06	2.15±0.12	2.97±0.14	4.19±0.31	5.39±0.35	4.99±0.16
Week 7	6.76±0.17	2.65±0.06	2.47±0.20	3.52±0.19	5.05±0.41	6.66±0.42	5.93±0.26
Week 8	7.99±0.16	2.81±0.06	2.68±0.20	4.11±0.25	6.30±0.47	7.92±0.47	7.55±0.44
Week 9	9.63±0.23	3.08±0.06	3.42±0.22	5.65±0.32	8.31±0.55	9.53±0.42	8.73±0.41
Week 10	10.42±0.23	3.22±0.09	3.98±0.33	6.72±0.37	9.17±0.48	10.17±0.33	9.54±0.37
Week 11	11.25±0.21	3.43±0.09	4.52±0.46	7.78±0.44	10.01±0.43	10.81±0.27	10.36±0.37
Week 12	12.06±0.20	3.64±0.08	5.10±0.53	8.69±0.41	10.36±0.36	11.05±0.24	10.81±0.35
Week 13	12.78±0.25	3.84±0.09	5.67±0.60	9.55±0.40	10.71±0.30	11.26±0.22	11.26±0.35

* Values are the average of growth radial readings with Std. Error of the 5 replicates for each isolates cultured in each media, statistical significance at $P < 0.05$ was determined using one-way ANOVA.

The fungus has some growth development in poor-nutrition media like agar media and slow growth rate detected in Czapek media (mainly a mixture of inorganic salts), as shown in (Figure 2-3A).

Figure 2-3 Growth parameters of *Venturia oleaginea* in different growing media. (A) Images of *Venturia oleaginea* isolates growth development in different media, from left: Agar, CZ, CZOL2:1, OLCZ1:1, OLCZ2:1, PDA, and OL, 13 weeks after inoculation, black and white background (B) *Venturia oleaginea* Growth chart in different media, statistical significance at $P < 0.05$ was determined using one-way ANOVA by comparing the means of isolates growth diameter vs. media, Bars represent values bind with standard error.

图 2-3 *Venturia oleaginea* 在不同生长培养基中的生长参数。(A) *Venturia oleaginea* 分离菌在不同培养基中的生长情况，黑白背景图像从左至右依次为：琼脂、CZ、CZOL2:1、OLCZ1:1、OLCZ2:1、PDA 和 OL（拍照时间为生长 13 周）(B) *Venturia oleaginea* 在不同培养基中的生长图，用单因素方差分析比较分离物生长直径的平均值，确定 $P < 0.05$ 时的统计学意义，条形图代表数值和标准误差。

Same as diameter, the colony mass obtained was the largest in PDA medium when comparing colony weight obtained from P2, Y41, M10, LS80 strains previously cultured in the

media with highest diameter growth: PDA, OLCZ 2: 1, and OL, and scraped off the surface of the culture media and weighed, the colonies average fresh weight was 0.26 g, 0.19535 g, and 0.125g, respectively (Figure 2-4A).

Figure 2-4 The harvested yield of *Venturia oleaginea* colonies. (A) The average of colonies fresh weight in three different media, 90 DAI. Statistical significance at $P < 0.05$ was determined using one-way ANOVA by comparing the means of isolates weight vs. media. Bars represent means values bind with standard error (B) The mycelia of 5 colonies isolated firstly in OLCZ1:1 for 30 days and sub-cultured in PDB for 45 days. (C, D) difference in harvested mycelia for colonies grew in PDB media at 26°C and 18°.

图 2-4 收获的 *Venturia oleaginea* 菌落。(A) 接种 90 天后三种不同培养基生长的菌落鲜重。(通过使用单向方差分析确定 $P < 0.05$ 的统计学显著性, 并比较分离物重量与培养基的平均值。条形代表均值和标准误差。)(B) 在 OLCZ1:1 中 培养 30 天的 5 个分离物的菌丝产量, 在 PDB 中亚培养 45 天。C、D: 在 26°C 和 18°C 的 PDB 培养基中生长的菌丝差异。

Furthermore, to estimate the dry weight which can be obtained by isolating the fungus in OLCA1:1 and then let it grow for 30 days then subcultured in PBD media for another 45 days to get a sufficient amount of mycelia; let to dry and weighed, the dry weight of (YUN41, M10, Xi 14, LS80, and P2 isolates) was: 0.214g, 0.139g, 0.174g, 0.188g, and 0.182g, respectively (Figure

2-4 B). In order to see the effect in later harvested mycelia yield, the incubation temperature of *V. oleaginea* was also examined at 26 °C and 18°C, one colony with 11.8 mm diameter was cut in half and grounded then cultured in two flasks containing PDB for 45 days and left to dry for three days and weighed as: 3.784 g and 0.958g at 18°C and 26°C, respectively (Figure 2-5 C, D).

2.3.3 Media pH. effect on the growth rate of *V. oleaginea* isolates.

The results showed that the variation in media pH. does not affect *V. oleaginea* growth. In the fourth week, for unknown reasons, isolates grown in media with a pH 7.5 showed a lower growth rate than the rest of the isolates (Fig. 2-5).

Figure 2-5 Effect of different pH. on the growth of *Venturia oleaginea* colonies. Statistical significance at $P < 0.05$ was determined using one-way ANOVA by comparing means of isolates diameter vs. media pH., bars represent the standard error.

图 2-5 不同 pH. 对 *Venturia oleaginea* 菌落生长的影响。采用单因素方差分析，比较分离菌直径与培养基 pH 值的平均值，在 $P < 0.05$ 时有统计学意义，条形图代表标准误差。

2.3.4 Morphological characters of the obtained isolates

Obtained colonies of *V. oleaginea* are circular-convex colonies with a dark greenish olivaceous surface that become brownish in older colonies, and the back is dark. It looks like a hemispherical body with surrounding-irregular halo margins that appeared clearly in OL and PDA media. The colonies' color variation is a little quiet, darker when colonies grow in liquid

media (Figure 2-3A, Figure 2-4C). Colonies do vary in growing style and the existence of asexual parts like conidiophores, conidia, and chlamydospores. The fungus under stress can produce heavy-melanized hyphae and different forms of chlamydospores.

The colonies consist of three layers, the submerged (appeared clearly in isolates growing in OL media), central, and aerial layers; the first layer consists of light-interwoven hyphae surrounding the central mass, while the main body is firm, thickly compacted, and not easy to cut, the aerial layer consists of copious hyphae and highly melanized.

In some dishes, few conidia were found within the first 30 days after isolation in (OLCZ1:1) medium, then no conidia detected in all media used (growing or isolating media). Chlamydospores (terminal or intercalary forms) were the main feature in all media introduced in this study and highly noticed in OLCZ1:1 and OLCZ2:1 media (Figure 2-6), later in sporulation induction experiment when fungus grew in pine needles based media combined with UV; new forms of chlamydospores were found in abundance in addition to conidia (Figure 2-9). In total, 88 isolates were obtained and identified as *V. oleaginea* using the single spore isolation method (Table 2-1).

Figure 2-6 Microscopic slides of *Venturia oleaginea* cultured in (OLCZ1:1), 30 DAI. (A) Colony under stereomicroscope 20x, (B) Mycelia (C) Hyphae (D-F) Chlamydospores (intercalary, terminal) and conidia were found in some isolates (E) Germinating chlamydospores (G-I) Conidia, and conidiophores. Scales: (A) 20X, (B) 100 μm , (C-F, I) 20 μm , (G-H) 10 μm .

图 2-6 接种 30 天后 *Venturia Oleaginea* 在 (OLCZ1:1) 中培养的显微照片。(A) 菌落在 20 倍立体显微镜下, (B) 菌丝 (C) 分生孢子 (D-F) 在一些分离菌中发现的厚垣孢子 (内生和顶生) 和分生孢子 (E) 发芽的厚垣孢子 (J-I) 分生孢子和分生孢子梗。标尺: (A) 放大 20 倍, (B) 100 μm , (C-F, I) 20 μm , (G-H) 10 μm 。

2.3.5 Confirmation of fungal species using PCR based markers

Five isolates were chosen randomly for molecular confirmation of species YUN41, M10, Xi 14, LS80, and P2. PCR product samples were identified by DNA sequencing with internal transcribed spacer (ITS4, ITS5) of nuclear ribosomal DNA (nrDNA), partial small subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (NS1 and NS4), and partial larger subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (LROR and LR5). The obtained band's size was compared with the band's size of molecular marker 4 (TIANGEN Biotech Beijing Co., Ltd) and sizes were approximately the same as the expected around 580, 1050, 920 bp, with ITS, SSU, and LSU, respectively (Figure 2-7). PCR products were sent for sequencing in (Zhejiang Youkang Biotechnology Co, Ltd). BLASTn search of *V. oleaginea* DNA sequences revealed high similarities to *V.oleaginea* sequences deposited in NCBI (Supplementary Table S2).

Figure 2-7 Gel electrophoresis images of DNA PCR products of *Venturia oleaginea*. (A) The five isolates selected for molecular confirmation, amplified with LSU, SSU, and ITS regions from the left, respectively (B) PCR products for DNA of a set of Chinese isolates from different areas cloned with SSU primers; bands with stars refer to strains included in the molecular confirmation of species.

图 2-7 *Venturia oleaginea* 的 DNA PCR 产物的凝胶电泳图像。(A) 对选取的 5 个分离株进行分子鉴定, 分别用 LSU、SSU、ITS 区域从左侧扩增 (B) 用 SSU 引物克隆的一组不同地区的中国分离株的 DNA PCR 产物, 带星号的条带是指被选为分子鉴定的菌株。

Phylogenetic analysis confirmed that all selected isolates belonged to *V. oleaginea* and grouped in the same clades with other *V. oleaginea* strains obtained from NCBI in the three phylogenetic trees constructed. As the Blastn search, *Fusicladium phillyreae*; the causing agent of Phillyrea scab disease, was found with the closest species to *V. oleaginea* strains and located in the same clades in ITS and LSU phylogenetic trees, other *Venturia* members were grouped in a separate clade in the phylogenetic tree constructed with ITS sequences or located in separates sub-clades in phylogenetic trees of LSU, SSU (Figure 2-8).

Figure 2-8 Phylogenetic relationships trees inferred using the Neighbor-Joining method. The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter method, the analysis involved 16 nucleotide sequences of the isolates: YUN41, M10, Xi 14, LS80 and most relative species sequences obtained by NCBI BLASTn to ITS, LSU, and SSU regions, *Fusarium oxysporum* partial sequences of ITS, LSU, and SSU regions (KF914478.1, AY118130.1, DQ831923.1) respectively, were used as out-group in the related tree.

图 2-8 利用近邻结合法构建的系统发育树。采用 Tamura 3 参数法计算进化距离，分析了 16 个分离株的核苷酸序列。YUN41、M10、Xi 14、LS80 以及 NCBI BLASTn 获得的 ITS、LSU、SSU 区域的大部分相对种序列，分别以 *Fusarium oxysporum* 的 ITS、LSU、SSU 区域的部分序列 (KF914478.1、AY118130.1、DQ831923.1) 作为外组。

2.3.6 Induction of *V. oleaginea* sporulation

Pine needles based media (PN, PNOL) induced the sporulation on *V. oleaginea*, while no conidia found in other media or media with additives (Figure 2-9 A, B, C). Two weeks of 12:12 hour's light/dark duration with fluctuation in day/night temperature showed no effect in *V. oleaginea* sporulation ability in all media or media with additives. It's noticed that conidia vanished after about 45 DAI, and only a few conidia were found in one isolate cultured in (PN0). 14 days of near UV showed a significant effect on re-generating sporulation in *V. oleaginea* isolates grown in pine needles based media (PN, PNOL), while no conidia found in other media or media with additives (Figure 2-9 D-L). The numbers of conidia detected after 14 days of UV exposure were documented, and statistical significance was determined using one way ANOVA by comparing means of conidia found in different PN-based media (Figure 2-10).

Figure 2-9 Microscopic slides of *Venturia oleaginea*. (A) Mycelia and germinating Chlamydospores, 30 DAI in PN media (B, C) Conidia forms, 30 DAI in PN media (D) Mycelia with conidia (E) harvested conidia (F, I, J) Highly melanized mycelia (G) Unicellular chlamydospores (H) hyphae with excessive chlamydospore (K, L) Conidia and conidiophores (D-L): isolates were cultured in PN media combined with 14 days of UV radiation. Scales: (A, C, F-L) 20 μ m, (D-E) 100 μ m, B: composite digital images with different scales.

图 2-9 *Venturiaoleaginea* 的显微照片。(A) 菌丝和发芽的厚垣孢子, 接种 30 天后在 PN 培养基中 (B, C) 的分生孢子, (D) 接种后 30 天在 PN 培养基中带有分生孢子的菌丝 (E) 收获的分生孢子 (F, I, J) 高度黑色化的菌丝 (G) 单细胞的分生孢子 (H) 带有厚垣孢子的菌丝 (K, L) 分生孢子和分生孢子梗 (D-L): 分离物在 PN 培养基中结合 14 天的紫外线照射培养。标尺: (A、C、F-L) 20 μ m, (D-E) 100 μ m, B: 不同比例的合成数字图像。

Figure 2-10 Effect of pine needles based media and other supplements combined with near UV radiation on *Venturia oleaginea* sporulation, statistical analysis carried out using one way ANOVA by comparing means of conidia found in different PN based media at $P < 0.05$, values of conidia concentration are the means of each media, bars represent the standard error.

图 2-10 以松针为基础的培养基和其他补充剂，结合近紫外线辐射对 *Venturia oleaginea* 产孢的影响，采用单因子方差分析进行统计分析，比较不同 PN 为基础的培养基中发现的孢子浓度平均值， $P < 0.05$ ，孢子浓度值为各培养基处理下的平均值，条形代表标准误差。

Contrary to expected, adding supplements like oleic acid, Casamino acid, and d-biotin negatively affected sporulation in isolates cultured in Pine needles-based media, and no effect can be detected in other media. Adding d-biotin to some colonies' growth side showed no sporulation effect. (Supplementary Table S3).

2.3.7 Plant inoculation with conidia obtained in artificial media

After successfully inducing *V. oleaginea* for sporulation, plant infection was conducted with conidia obtained *in-vitro*. After one month of inoculation, initial symptoms of olive leaf scab caused by the pathogenic fungi *V. oleaginea* were observed in three olive seedlings (Picual cv.), in which 10 leaves were inoculated with (10^5 /ml) conidial inoculum on each plant, 3-4 leaves were infected. At the same time, mycelial cuts failed to infect the plant. The infected leaves were susceptible to any movement or wind due to pathogen invasion, causing defoliation

due to dead cells of petiole bases, which became black color. Infected leaves that stayed connected to the plant fell off after about 70 days of the inoculation (Figure 2-12).

Figure 2- 11 Inoculation and plant infection with the fungal pathogen *Venturia oleaginea* (A) Inoculated olive (Picual cv.) (B) *Venturia oleaginea* isolates (source of inoculum) cultured in Pine+ UV treatment (C) Prepared mycelia-cuts inoculum (D-L) Same-view of lesions development at surfaces of the infected leaves.

图 2-11 真菌病原体 *Venturia oleaginea* 的接种和植物感染状。(A) 接种橄榄品种 (Picual cv.) (B) 在 Pine+紫外线处理中培养的 *Venturia Oleaginea* 分离株 (接种源) (C) 准备好的菌丝体-切割接种物 (D-L) 在不同时间拍摄的感染叶片表面的病灶。

In June 2020, we isolated the pathogen again from the infected plant; single spores from the lesions of infected leaves isolated in OLCZ 1:1 media grew for about 30 days and showed the

same morphological traits of *V. oleaginea*, then sub-cultured in PDA media (Figure 2-12). The results confirmed that the pathogen we isolated caused olive leaf scab to match Koch's postulation.

Figure 2- 12 Confirmation of the causal agent of olive leaf scab. (A-C) *Venturia oleaginea* colonies isolated from the inoculated plants using single spore isolation methods and cultured in OLCZ1:1 media (B-C) 20-120 days after sub-culturing in PDA (D) Olive leaf scab lesion under the stereomicroscope.

图 2-12 橄榄叶斑病原体的确认 (A-C) 利用单孢子分离方法从接种植物中分离出的 *Venturia oleaginea* 菌落，并在 OLCZ1:1 培养基中培养，(B-C) 在 PDA 中亚培养后 20-120 天。(D) 立体显微镜拍摄的橄榄叶病灶。

2.4 Discussion

The isolation of the pathogenic fungus *V. oleaginea* is extremely difficult and time-consuming [84]. Also, the knowledge at the molecular level is very poor. The lack of knowledge about *V.oleagineae* was mainly due to two main reasons; one is the isolation problems mentioned before, and the other is the inability of the obtained isolates to produce conidia, which are the only known source as an inoculum to infect the host plant [30]; thus the application of "molecular Koch's postulates" and the study of pathogenicity at the molecular level which is one of the basics of studying host-pathogen interaction is still inapplicable to this pathogen.

When we started our work on *V. oleaginea*, we had two goals in mind that were among our targets. The first is to accelerate the isolation process to save the later experiments' time and induce fungus sporulation, which may lead to infecting the plant with artificially produced conidia. Olive leaves extracted media was the main media used to obtain the pure strains [55, 56, 58] with a variation of the time required for the isolation process, our results in the same line with others in getting pure strains from single spore isolates, but failed to get the pure ones when we tried to isolate the fungus from the host tissues; we supposed that this fungus is sensitive to chemicals that we used to sterilize the leaf surface as the fungus colonized in the outer cuticular layer in infected leaves [18]. From the other side, isolation in liquid media mentioned by other researchers showed good results but the number of isolates obtained were very few according to the experiment design and their targets, liquid media like PDB and liquid Czapek sucrose media may be a good way to get the pure strains, but the variations in isolation conditions and obtained results were clearly different, particularly in the optimum temperature for *V. oleaginea* developing which is between 15-20°C, for example the isolation time from single spore inoculation to DNA extraction was 2 months at 15° C and one month at 26 °C [57, 60] respectively, these results contradicted the results of others researchers who isolated the fungus and obtained plenty of strains [56, 58] and also contradicted the results that we got, for example; Obanor got the pure strains from New Zealand Orchards by culturing single spores in olive leaves extract media at 15 °C for 3-6 months to get about 0.25g of mycelium, while Bernaschina, Leoni and Alaniz [58] used olive leaves extract at 17 °C for the development of the conidia germ tube and then transferred the germinated conidia to PDA media at 17 °C and estimated the growth rate in both media (OLE and PDA) and extracted DNA after about 3 months. This method used to get the

pure isolates was similar to the one we used with the exception of the primary media for the development of the conidia germ tube which was 4% agar media and mainly used to facilitate the transfer of the germinated conidia to permanent media (OLCZ 1:1), and also for its low detection ability for the airborne fungi [85]. Our results proposed the OLCZ 1:1 media as the best media to isolate *V. oleaginea* among all media introduced in the study, with pure isolates percentage reaching 48%.

After the determination of the isolation media, the growth rates of the fungus were estimated by culturing it in several media. Our results showed that the isolation medium OLCZ:1 is the best medium for *V. oleaginea* spore initial growth and colony formation, since until the 3rd week after culturing OLCZ1:1 media was leading in growth rates among other media, then kind of balance occurred in growth readings between PDA, OLCZ1:1, and OLCZ 2:1, this balance and nearly equal growth development extends until reaching the 9th week, then PDA leading alone and showing good growth readings.

Bernaschina, Leoni and Alaniz [58] compared the growth rate between PDA and olive leaves media at 17 °C and found that fungus cultured in PDA medium had a good growth rate at (0.27 mm / day), while in olive leaves media is only at 0.16 mm/ day; our results are in the same line with their results with the mention that the initial disc size of colonies they used was 3 mm, while we used 1 mm as initial size for colonies development.

Also, results have shown that *V. oleaginea* needs a combination of media extracted from the host tissue (OL) and in-organic salts media (Czapek) to induct the initial growth from germinated conidia and later when the colony formed, the fungus needs rich media like PDA to develop and continue growing, this was obviously clear in plates containing PDA, OLCZ mixtures, and OL media when the fungus continued growing in PDA at good rates, at the same time, in other media, growth nearly stopped after 3-4 months. Our results showed that PDA, OLCZ2:1, OL media are the best media for fungus growth within the three months of experiment duration.

The ability of fungi or any organism to sense and adapt to environmental changes is fundamental to surviving, and fungi have developed several mechanisms to adapt to pH. Variations [86]. *V. oleaginea*, as specific to olive may need the same pH. level as the host tissue, previously Mahmoud [87] studied the impact of different factors including pH on the germination

of *V. oleaginea* spores, he found that conidia can germinate in wide range pH between 5-12, and no study showed the effect of pH on *V.oleaginae* growth yet.

pH. of fresh olive leaves grounded was determined in our laboratory about 5, the media introduced in our experiment were prepared with a wide pH range (4.5- 9.5). Results showed no significant difference in growth rates of *V. oleaginea* when using various pH levels on the growth rates of the obtained colonies, and thus the fungus can adapt to a wide pH range.

Fungi have developed the ability to detect and respond to various environmental changes to survive; one of these strategies is that fungi can deal with multiple stresses by changing their morphology ^[88]. Previously, morphology characters of the pathogenic fungus *V. oleaginea* like colors, mycelium texture, and asexual parts were mentioned by some researchers. The number of published photos for the colonies and asexual parts obtained *in-vitro* are very few; in this paper, we hope that we have added more knowledge to the fungus' morphological characters' understanding process.

Colonies' colors, growth style, asexual parts, and slow rates are the main aspects to describe *V. oleaginea* isolates in addition to the conidia shape obtained from the infected leaves ^[55, 56, 58]; also, asexual parts of *V. oleaginea* were described in brief before, Viruega, Moral, Roca, Navarro and Trapero ^[89] found that the pathogen developed sclerotia or stroma-like with a pseudoparenchymal spherical tissue similar to immature pseudothecia of *Venturia* species in about 5% of infected leaves placed on the soil surface, and chlamydospores were observed in 10% of the leaves in the same condition. Benkada, Belhoucine, Benhamed and Berrebbah ^[55] found the chlamydospores in isolates obtained from single spore isolation. Our study identified at least two forms of chlamydospores (terminal, intercellular) and highly melanized aggregated chlamydospores and unicellular chlamydospores; also, we introduced the conidia produced in artificial media for the first time.

Morphological and cultural features of many fungi are often simple and may show considerable phenotypic variation between species. These features are based on both; sexual and asexual stages of the fungus. *V. oleaginea*, the fungus belongs to Deuteromycetes fungi with no sexual cycle known yet (anamorph), leads to morphological identification based on the asexual stage, such classification may not reflect the right phylogenetic relationships; therefore, the

molecular-based identification method should be a useful tool for the genetic identification of fungi.

Many universal sequences can be used as markers to study the differences at the DNA level of different species; one widely used example is the rRNA cistron [77], which contains both highly conserved and variable regions: 18S, 5.8S, and 28S rRNA genes, universal primers synthesized from the previous regions can amplify this gene's regions from nearly any fungal species, [77, 90].

Our molecular investigations and NCBI blast results revealed high similarities with *V. oleaginea*. In the three phylogenetic trees constructed, the sequences of selected isolates were grouped in one mixed cluster with other *V. oleaginea* sequences, the presence of *Fusicladium phillyreae* within these clusters in ITS, and LSU phylogenetic trees could be due to the same geographic origin of both host plants belonging to Oleaceae family, and the evolution between two fungus could be a kind of sibling pathogen resulting from chance mutations as well as from hybridization [91]. This genetic similarity between the two species was also reported by other researchers [92].

It's known that some plant tissues are effective in inducing sporulation; for example, Pine tree needles media induce some fungi sporulation [66]. Yoshida and Shirata [73] found that biotin has an inducing effect for sporulation in anthracnose fungus(*Colletotrichum dematium*) attacking mulberry when isolates were grown on media containing Australian pine needle, and biotin can alter the synthesis of wall polysaccharides and oleic acid and thus trigger the selective expression of genes involved in sporulation [93-97].

Also, the media that contains favorable fatty acids to fungi like oleic acid may lead to inducing the conidium germination and induce sporulation in some fungi. [76, 98]. Hexan extraction method to extract fatty acid in leaves of different olive varieties indicated that olive leave extraction contains 18.2-22.24% of oleic acid from total fatty acids founds [99]. Accordingly, we supposed that because *V. oleaginea* is a specific pathogen to olive and produce conidia only when living in host tissue, it may need oleic acid for sporulation; our results indicate that adding oleic acids, combination amino acids (Casamino), and vitamins like biotin have no inducing effect in *V. oleaginea* sporulation.

Different UV radiation levels can affect sporulation in some fungi; for example, [100] used 295 nm UV radiation to induce sporulation in *Bipolaris oryzaeand*, they found that the harvested spores yield is inversely related to increased exposure to UV rays. Leach [101] used blue light and near UV radiation to induce 34 species of fungi for sporulation, and he reported that the UV might be the main inducer in some species; this is somehow what we found related to *V. oleaginea* since the ingredients of pine needles tree medium are the base in sporulation inducing, but this sporulation phenomenon was vanished quickly due to the ability of the fungus to adapt to the new environment and the nutritional supplements that have been added to this media may have helped in this adaptation, this also goes well with the findings of Su, Qi and Cai [66] when they mentioned that low nutrients media is another inducer for fungus to produce the spores.

Several researchers study the volatile oily and other components of pine needle conifer trees; the main components found were: α -pinene, germacrene D, β -caryophyl, and β -pinene in addition to other volatile components like alcohols, carbonyl compounds, esters, and carboxylic acids [102-107], however, these components differ according to pine tree variety, and extraction method. Jung, You, Moon and Lee [108] studied the effect of main compounds reported as inhibitors for pathogenic fungi which existed in most pine trees (acetol, furfural, 5-methyl furfural, and terpine-4-ol) on inhibition of plant pathogenic fungus *Alternaria mali*; in which they found that all of the four previous components have various significant effects in growth inhibition.

In our study, we didn't notice this inhibition in *V. oleaginea* growth; and this may due to the defensive measures taken by *V. oleaginea* like melanin production, which provide defense against environmental stresses such as UV, oxidizing agents, and ionizing radiation. Melanin also helps fungi to survive in tough environments and play a role in fungal pathogenesis [109].

Including highly susceptible olive cultivars to olive leaves scab disease is an essential element in this study; Pecual was reported as a susceptible cultivar for olive scab [27, 110], while Picholine is very tolerant[111], and no information about the Chinese cultivar EZ-8, even though we found severe infection with the three cultivars during our sampling. The nine olive seedlings inoculated in *V. oleaginea* were bought as healthy seedlings and grew in soil pots about two years prior to the experiment time. Our inoculation experiment results ensured the susceptibility of the Picual olive cultivar cultivated in China for infection of olive leaf scab disease.

2.5 Conclusion

Venturia oleaginea is the main pathogenic fungus attacking olive trees in major cultivation areas around the world. However, isolation of the fungal pathogen strains is an arduous process. The pathogen is also hard to produce conidia in artificial media. In this study, we isolated the fungus using our innovative media, confirmed the species by morphological and molecular identifying, and succeeded in inducing pathogen for sporulation to infect the host plant. We suggest olive leaves extraction-Czapek media (OLCZ1:1) as an isolation medium with a success rate reaching up to 48%. PDA and (OLCZ 2:1) media were found to have the highest diameter growth rate. Pine needles based media induced the fungus for sporulation while other media/ techniques failed or rare conidia found. UV light combined with pine media has an excellent effect, showing the ability to re-induce sporulation in the pine needle media since the pathogen adapted very fast to culturing media and lose the ability to produce conidia over time. The inoculated plants with conidia obtained from the artificial media showed clear symptoms after eight weeks, while the symptoms development period in inoculated leaves needs more than 12 weeks to have the symptoms similar to eye-bird. This study will guide the interested researchers by introducing a good method to isolate and cultivate the fungus, exhibit some features of the fungus colonies that grow in artificial media, showing the genetic relations between the closest *Venturia* species, and introduce the method to induce pathogen sporulation to infect the host plant.

Chapter 3 Genome sequence of *Venturia oleaginea*, the causal agent of olive leaf scab

3.1 Introduction

Olive leaf scab, also known as olive leaf spot or peacock spot disease, is a fungal scab disease specific to olive trees. *Venturia oleaginea* (Castagne) Rossman & Crous (synonyms *Spilocaea oleagina* (castagne) S. Hughes and *Fusicladium oleagineum* (Castagne) Ritschel & U. Braun), the causal agent is a pathogenic fungus belonging to the phylum Ascomycota, Pleosporales, Venturiaceae. The fungus was reported for the first time in France [26] and is widespread in the Mediterranean olive producing countries as well as other countries with the same weather conditions. The pathogen, which has a biotrophic mode of nutrition, can cause early defoliation of olive trees, leading to poor growth and yield reduction^[62]. Yield losses may reach up to 20% [27]. Trees with a dense canopy increase the humidity in the grove, which increases the prevalence of leaf scab in wet weather conditions [15].

Knowledge of this pathogen at the molecular level is poor due to the technical challenges of working with a biotrophic organism. *V. oleaginea* is difficult to isolate taking up to 6 months to culture sufficient quantities of mycelium for DNA isolation, and it rarely produces conidia on artificial media [56, 60]. No sexual stage of *V. oleaginea* is currently known, although indirect evidence of recombination comes from the observation that all isolates collected in the major olive-growing regions of Uruguay have unique genotypes [18, 58, 89].

Until now, seven members of the genus *Venturia* have been sequenced, including *V. effusa*, *V. inaequalis*, *V. asperata*, *V. pirina*, *V. Nashicola*, *V. aucupariae*, *V. carpophila*, the causal pathogen of pecan scab, apple scab, pear scab, sorbus scab, peach scab [112-118] respectively. Genome sequencing of *V. oleaginea* will provide greater options for more effective identification of the fungus, study of genes of interest such as those involved in host recognition, fungicide resistance, and mating-type genes, and development of specific molecular markers for population genetic diversity analysis.

The term comparative genomics refers to the field of biological research in which the genomic features of different organisms are compared^[119, 120]. Comparative of genomic of some

features of *Venturia* species genomes will give additional insight view of these organisms. This comparative may include DNA sequences, genes, phylogenetic, secondary metabolism, and other genomic structural landmarks. The primary principle in comparing genomes is that standard features of two organisms will often be encoded within the evolutionarily conserved DNA between them to compare the genome features. Therefore the approaches start with making some form of alignment between genomes sequences and looking for orthologous sequences in the aligned sequences; based on these, molecular evolution can be inferred [121, 122].

Secondary metabolites (SMs) produced by Fungi are divided into four main chemical classes, including polyketides (PKs), non-ribosomal peptides (NRPs), indole alkaloids, and terpenes, or hybrid classes like PK-NRPs [123]. In most cases, the genes involved in these classes' production are grouped into gene clusters and called secondary gene clusters. Until 2016, there were 15,600 secondary metabolite compounds produced by different fungi species, among it about 353 produced by Dothideomycetes fungi [124].

3.2 Material and methods:

3.2.1 Fungal material and DNA extraction

V. oleaginea mono-sporal isolate YUN 35 was isolated from an infected olive leaf (cv. Pecual) collected from Yunnan Academy of Forestry Garden, Kunming, Yunnan, China, and cultured with olive leaf extract agar media described in Obanor [29] for about three months, then transferred to liquid olive leaf extract media to get a good amount of mycelia.

The genomic DNA was extracted using the CTAB method [125]. The Nanodrop spectrophotometer checked the DNA quality to ensure a concentration of around 100 µg/ml and the quality of OD260/280=1.8–2.0.

3.2.2 Species confirmation

The strain identification was confirmed based on the DNA sequence of the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) amplified with primers ITS4 and ITS5 [77], partial small subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (SSU) region amplified with primers NS1 and NS4 [77], and partial larger subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (LSU) region amplified with LROR and LR5 [78]. PCR thermal cycles and conditions described previously in chapter 2 (Table 2-2). PCR products were sent for

sequencing in (Zhejiang Youkang Biotechnology Co, Ltd). The obtained sequences were blasted against *Venturia oleaginea* species in the NCBI blast tool, aligned using MEGA X [80]. Phylogenetic trees were calculated by the neighbor-Joining method [81]. Bootstrap analysis was performed 1000 times to confirm the produced trees' reliability [82], and the evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter method [83]. *Fusarium oxysporum* partial sequences of ITS, LSU, and SSU regions (*KF914478.1*, *AY118130.1*, *DQ831923.1*), respectively, were used as out-group in each tree.

3.2.3 Sequencing and assembly

The isolate YUN35 was sent for sequencing in Beijing Novogene Bioinformatics Technology Co. Ltd, using PacBio Sequel platform. One single-molecule real-time (SMRT) cell data was generated, and the low-quality reads with SMRT link (v6.0.) were filtered, and finally 6.58 Gb of long-read data (143 X genome coverage, N50 11 kb and average length 7kb) was obtained. Then, we conducted de novo genome assembly using HGAP4 (Expected Genome Length = 45 Mb), a pipeline in SMRT Link. The pre-assembly was polished using the Arrow algorithm (<https://github.com/PacificBiosciences/GenomicConsensus>) by mapping raw long reads back to the pre-assembled genome and generated final polished genome assembly.

The completeness of YUN35 assembly was assessed using BUSCO v3.0 (Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs) [126] and evaluated with Ascomycota data set (n=1,315) and fungal dataset (n=290). Finally, The obtained genome sequence assembly was evaluated with QUAST [127]. Assemblies comparatives between *V. olaginea* genome and other *Venturia* members was performed using GensAS v6.0 [128]

3.2.4 Gene prediction and functional annotation

Repeats were masked by RepeatMasker v4.0.9 using de novo repeats library generated by RepeatModeler v1.08. The soft-repeat-masked (repeats region in low case not masked with N) assembly was used for the gene predictions using AUGUSTUS v3.3.3 [129], integrating the RNA-seq data of the isolate YUN35 mycelia cultured in potato dextrose broth in the dark with shaking at 18°C.

Gene functional annotation is carried out by different softwares and relevant database, including InterProScan (<https://github.com/ebi-pf-team/interproscan/wiki>), a software package that allows sequences to be scanned against InterPro's signatures (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/interpro>)^[130], and Pfam (<http://pfam.xfam.org>), a database of an extensive collection of protein families. We also employed eggNOGmapper (<http://eggnog-mapper.embl.de/>) online server which using precomputed eggNOG v5.0 (<http://eggnogdb.embl.de/>) orthology clusters database to assigned annotations including GO (Gene Ontology, <http://geneontology.org/>), KEGG (Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes, <https://www.kegg.jp/>), and COG (Cluster of Orthologous Group, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/COG/>). Candidate secreted proteins were characterized by the protein length \leq 400 amino acids, containing signal peptide (signalP) and without transmembrane helices in mature protein (TMHMM).

3.2.5 Phylogenetic analysis based on the whole genome sequence

A whole genome-based phylogeny analysis was carried out by two methods: 1st is by identifying the orthologous single-copy genes from 8 genomes. TransDecoder (version 5.5.0) was used to identify potential coding regions within all the genomes and Open Reading frames (ORFs). The best reading frames (ORF) were kept and compared with each genome with OrthoFinder version 2.5.2^[131]; utility was used with Diamond protocol to identify the orthologous genes and compare them in all 8 mentioned species. The tree was finally viewed in Dendroscope (3). The 2nd method conducted with REALPHY 1.13^[132] webtool, on it, all provided sequences will be mapped to each of the reference(*V. effusa* used as reference genome) via bowtie2. The output multiple sequence alignment file was used to build the phylogenetic tree by using MEGA X^[80].

3.2.6 Secondary metabolism comparative analysis

AntiSMASH fungal 4.0.0^[133], a web-based analysis platform with default parameter settings, was used to find the secondary metabolism gene clusters in assembled YUN35 genome and other published *Venturia* sp. genomes obtained from NCBI database. Blast analysis and gene annotation were carried out using NCBI genome portal software. Obtained results were compared within different genomes. Predicted results of the obtained secondary gene clusters

were carried out as reported in [134]. Secondary metabolism gene clusters were determined using AntiSMASH fungal 4.0.0 [133], a web-based analysis platform with default parameters setting.

3.3 Results:

3.3.1 Colony morphology

The colony morphology of isolate YUN35 is circular, convex, grayish-green, texture floccose, reverse black. These are similar to the morphological traits described by Benkada, Belhoucine, Benhamed and Berrebbah [55].

Figure 3-1 Mono-spore isolate YUN35 cultured in olive leaf extract media.

图 3-1 橄榄叶提取物培养基中培养的单孢子分离株 YUN35。

3.3.2 Molecular confirmation

The NCBI blast against obtained sequences revealed high similarities to deposited *Venturia oleaginea* species sequences, which comes first highest similarity species according to blast with ITS and LSU sequences, while *Venturia inaequalis* became first in SSU (Table 3-1).

Table 3-1 Description table of blast results of the YUN35 sample amplified with internal transcribed spacer (ITS) gene region, small subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (SSU) region, partial larger subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (LSU) region, first three of each respectively.

表 3-1 内转录间隔 (ITS) 基因区、小亚基核糖体 DNA (SSU) 区、部分大亚基核糖体 DNA (LSU) 区扩增的 YUN35 样品 blastn 结果描述表 (分别为前三位)。

Scientific Name	Total Score	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession	References
<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i>	1061	100%	99.83	EU035435.1	[135]
<i>Venturia oleaginea</i>	1055	100%	99.65	EU035434.1	[135]
<i>Venturia oleaginea</i>	1031	97%	99.82	KF766166.1	[136]
<i>V. inaequalis</i>	1921	99%	99.53	EF114737.1	[137]
<i>uncultured Pezizomycotina</i>	1916	99%	99.43	EU647053.1	[138]
<i>V.pyrina</i>	1916	99%	99.43	EF114739.1	[137]
<i>V. oleaginea</i>	1679	97%	99.89	EU035434.1	[135]
<i>V. chlorospora</i>	1677	99%	99.14	DQ384101.1	[139]
<i>V. chlorospora</i>	1663	97%	99.45	EU035454.1	[135]

The phylogenetic analyses set YUN35 with other *V.oleaginea* from other regions in the same group in the three trees (ITS, LSU, SSU). The supporting values (bootstrap) were 54, 94, 99 in LSU, SSU, ITS based trees, respectively (Figure 3-2).

Figure 3-2 Phylogenetic relationships trees inferred using the Neighbor-Joining method. The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter method, the analysis involved 9 nucleotide sequences of the isolates: YUN35 and most relative species sequences obtained by NCBI BLASTn to SSU, LSU, and ITS regions, *Fusarium oxysporum* partial sequences of ITS, LSU, and SSU regions (KF914478.1, AY118130.1, DQ831923.1) respectively, were used as out-group in the related tree.

图 3-2 利用近邻结合法方法推断的系统发育关系树。采用 Tamura 3 参数法计算进化距离，分析了 9 个分离株的核苷酸序列。YU35 以及 NCBI BLASTn 获得的 SSU、LSU、ITS 区域的大部分相对种序列，分别以 *Fusarium oxysporum* 的 ITS、LSU、SSU 区域的部分序列 (KF914478.1、AY118130.1、DQ831923.1) 作为相关树的外组。

The ITS, SSU, and LSU sequences of YUN 35 have been deposited in GenBank, and the accession numbers are MT379576, MT379578, and MT379577, respectively.

3.3.3 *Venturia oleaginea* isolate (YUN35) Genome features

A total of 7.64Gb raw PacBio reads were generated by PacBio Sequel platform. After filtering short reads < 1kb, finally a total of 6.58 Gb (86.06% of raw reads, reads N50: 11,027 bp) long-read data was used for de novo genome assembly using HGAP4 in SMRT-Link software (Table 3-2). The average read length was 7,285 bp and maximum read length was 58,279 bp (Table 3-2 and Figure 3-3). We finally obtained a 46.08-Mb genome assembly (GC content: 48.62%) consist of 61 contigs with N50 of 1.80 Mb, maximum contig length of 2.54 Mb and average contig length of 0.76 Mb, (Table 3-3, and Figure 3-4). The evaluation of genome assembly with QUAST^[127] in comparison with *V. effuse* as a reference is shown in (Figure 3-4).

Table 3-2 Features of PacBio reads used for de novo genome assembly.
表 3-2 用于从头基因组组装的 PacBio 读序的特征。

Reads parameters	Value
Total size of raw reads	7,643,135,346
Percent of raw reads used for assembly	86.06%
Mean concordance (accuracy)	87.73%
Number of subreads	902,954
Total size of subread (bp)	6,577,682,279
Subread length mean (bp)	7,285
Subread length N50 (bp)	11,027
Subread length max (bp)	58,279

Figure 3-3 Length distribution (A) and concordance (B) of subreads used for genome assembly.
图 3-3 用于基因组组装的读序长度分布(A)和一致性(B)。

Table 3-3 Statistics of the whole Genome assemblies of *Venturia oleaginea* isolate YUN35.

表 3-3 *Venturia oleaginea*分离株YUN35的全基因组组合统计。

Assembly parameters	YUN35
Sequencing platform	PacBio sequel
Assembly method	HGAP 4
Genome size (Mb)	46.08
Sequencing coverage	143 X
Number of contig	61
Average contig length (Mb)	0.76
Contig N50 (Mb)	1.80
Maximum contig length (Mb)	2.54
Contigs with telomere repeats (TTAGGG) _n /(CCCTAA) _n /both	16/10/2
GC content % *	48.62
Repeats %	23.02
BUSCO's genome complete in <i>ascomycota</i> (N=1315)	Genome: 94.5%, Gene: 95.7%
BUSCO's genome complete in fungi (N=290)	Genome: 96.9%, Gene: 96.2%
Genes	11540
Candidate secreted proteins	581
Annotated genes	9516

Figure 3- 4 QAST genome evaluation report. (A) contigs size viewer of the YUN35 genome, total length is 46.08, 61 contigs in total. (B) Cumulative length of contigs, Contigs are ordered from largest to smallest. (C) GC content.

图3-4 QAST基因组评估报告。(A)是YUN35基因组的重叠群大小查看器，总长度为46.08，共61个重叠群。(B)重叠群的累积长度，重叠群从大到小排序。(C)GC含量。

The assembly parameters of the YUN35 genome compared to *V. effuse*, and *V. inquilalis*, and *V. Carpophila* are presented in (Table 3-3).

Table 3-4 Sequences assembly parameters for *Venturia oleaginea*, *V. effuse*, *V. carpophila*, and *V. inquilalis*
表 3-4 *Venturia oleaginea*, *V. effuse*, *V. Carpophila* 和 *V. inquilalis* 的序列组装参数。

Genome	<i>V. oleaginea</i>	<i>V. effuse</i>	<i>V. Carpophila</i>	<i>V. inquilalis</i>
Size	46,084,733bp	45,351,275bp	35,867,442bp	72,791,559bp
N50	1802151bp	2472196bp	2019624bp	2978635bp
N75	1172999bp	2039178bp	1406016bp	1856644bp
N90	527280bp	1626195bp	741945bp	1492844bp
N95	287989bp	1476534bp	358418bp	897477bp
Mean	755487.43	2159584.52	1086892.18	1102902.41
Good sequences:	61 input contigs (100.00%)	21 input contigs (100.00%)	33 input contigs (100.00%)	66 input contigs (100.00%)

Among *V.oleaginea* contigs, 16 and 10 contigs contain telomere repeats (TTAGGG)_n and (CCCTAA)_n at the distal end respectively. Interestingly, two contigs of 1.90 Mb and 1.83 Mb have telomere repeats at both ends, which indicates that these two contigs represent entire chromosomes (Table 3-2). Based on telomere representation, the *V. oleaginea* has at least 16 chromosomes, which is similar to the number of 20 chromosomes identified in a recent chromosome level assembly for *V. effusa* isolate FRT5LL7^[118].

BUSCO v3.0 assesment and evaluation with the ascomycota data set (n=1,315) showed 94.5% completeness with 1243 complete, 40 fragmented and 32 missing BUSCO orthologs. Whereas evaluation with the fungal dataset (n=290) showed 96.2% completeness with 281 complete, 3 fragmented, and 6 missing BUSCO orthologs. The BUSCO completeness assesment at gene level showed that 95.7% completeness with the ascomycota data set (n=1,315) while 96.2% completeness with the fungi dataset (n=290) (Figure 3-5).

Figure 3-5 Assessment of YUN35 assembly completeness

图 3-5 YUN35 装配完整性评估

3.3.4 Genome annotation

Approximately 23.02% of the genome was associated with repetitive sequences, identified by RepeatMasker v4.0.9 based de-novo repeat library generated by RepeatMoldeler. Most of the repeats were interspersed repeats (22.49%), including 1.45% LTR, 7.20% LINEs, 6.11 % DNA elements, and 7.73 % Unclassified, while the rest repeats belong to simple repeats (0.47%) and low complexity (0.07%) (Figure 3-6).

Figure 3-6 Repeats in YUN35 genome assembly.

图3-6 YUN35基因组组装中的重复序列。

A total of 11540 genes were found after combining RNA-seq and de novo strategy. Gene annotation analysis showed that there were 581 candidate secreted proteins (Table 3-3), and a total of 9516 genes (82.5%) can be annotated by Pfam 32.0 (<http://pfam.xfam.org>), GO (<http://geneontology.org/>), KEGG (<https://www.kegg.jp/>), and COG. (Figure 3-7).

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Figure 3-7 Identified and annotated genes and genes families with (A) Pfam (B) eggNOG (C) KEGG and (D) gene ontology (GO) pathways.

图 3-7 通过 (A) Pfam (B) eggNOG (C) KEGG 和 (D) GO 途径识别和注释的基因和基因家族。

Pfam annotation showed that proteins associated with Major facilitator superfamily (PF07690), Protein kinase domain (PF00069), and fungal specific transcription factor domain (PF04082) in the top 3 terms (Figure 3-7 A). COG classification showed that about 2377 genes with unknown function, 624 genes with post-translational modification protein turnover-chaperones functions, 611 carbohydrates transport and metabolism functional genes, and 515 genes of amino acid transport and metabolism functions in the top terms (Figure 3-7 B). KEGG result shown that most proteins in pathways referred to Carbohydrate metabolism, Amino acid metabolism, Translation, and Transport and catabolism (Figure 3-7 C). GO annotations classified genes into three categories: molecular function, cellular component, and biological process (Figure 3-7 D).

The genome sequence and annotation file have been deposited into NCBI under the BioProject accession number PRJNA595014.

3.3.5 Phylogenetic analysis based on the whole genome sequence

In both trees were created, the *Venturia* members have separated into two main groups of *V. aucupariae*, *V. inquilalis*, *V. nachicola*, *V. pyrina*, and *V. oleaginea* in the first group and *V. effuse*, *V. carpophila*, and *V. asperata* in the other one. These two main groups are also divided into two subgroups (sub-clusters), and each cluster in both trees has the same *Venturia* members where (*V. nachicola*, *V. pyrina*) were determined as a twin, same as for (*V. inquilalis*, *V. aucupariae*), and (*V. asperata*, *V. carpophila*). *V. effuse* was found is closer to *V. asperata*, and *V. carpophila* while *V. oleaginea* closer to (*V. inquilalis*, *V. aucupariae*, *V. nachicola*, and *V. pyrina*) (Figure 3-8).

Figure 3-8 Phylogenetic analyses (A) built using TransDecoder (version 5.5.0) by identifying the orthologous single-copy genes from *Venturia* genomes. (B) Constructed using REALPHY 1.13 pipeline, then the evolutionary tree was inferred using the Maximum Parsimony method. The most parsimonious tree with a length = 1783 is shown. The consistency index is (0.620278), the retention index is (0.519497).

图 3-8 系统发育分析 (A) 通过使用 TransDecoder (5.5.0 版) 识别文图拉基因组中的正交单拷贝基因建立系统发育分析。(B) 使用 REALPHY 1.13 流水线构建, 然后使用最大简约法推断进化树。最简约树的长度=1783, 如图所示, 其一致性指数为 (0.620278), 保留指数为 (0.519497)。

3.3.6 Secondary metabolism comparative

Fourteen gene clusters of secondary metabolism were found in *Venturia oleaginea* isolate YUN35 (Table 3-5 and Figure 3-9). Most similar like-cluster duclauxin, and melanin were found in *V. oleaginea* and *V. asperata*. Melanin gene cluster found in all *Venturia* members, others like:6-methylsalicylic acid found in *V. effuse* and *V. pirina* and compactin found in *V. effuse* and *V. pirina*, squalestatin in *V. aucupariae*, and monacolin K in *V. carpophila*.

Table 3-5 Identified secondary metabolite gene clusters.

表 3-5 已确定的次生代谢物基因簇。

Secondary metabolisms	NRPS	NRPS-like	Terpenes	T1PKS	indole	NAPAA	siderophore	Total
<i>V. oleaginea</i>	3	4	2	3	2	0	0	14
<i>V. effuse</i>	2	5	3	3	2	0	0	15
<i>V. inaequalis</i> ,	5	5	3	5	2	1	1	22
<i>V. asperata</i>	3	4	5	4	2	0	0	18
<i>V. pirina</i>	3	6	2	7	1	0	0	19
<i>V. Nashicola</i>	3	5	2	2	2	0	0	14
<i>V. aucupariae</i>	3	7	2	5	1	0	0	18
<i>V. carpophila</i>	2	5	3	3	2	0	0	15

Abbreviations: NRPS: Non-ribosomal peptide synthetase cluster, NRPS-like fragment, NAPAA:non-alpha poly-amino acids like e-Polylysin, Type I PKS (Polyketide synthase).

At least 80 chemical compounds have been detected, produced by five gene clusters as NPRS involved in 30, NRPS-LIKE in 18, T1PKS in 25, terpenes in 5, and only two compounds were detected produced by indole SMs (**Supplementary Table S4**).

Figure 3-9 Secondary metabolism gene clusters identified in 8 *Venturia* members genomes.

图 3-9 在 8 个 *Venturia* 成员基因组中发现的次生代谢基因簇。

3.4 Conclusion

The olive leaf scab, also known as peacock spot disease caused by *Venturia oleagina* (syn. *Spilocaea oleagina* and *Fusicladium oleagineum*) is the most widespread and economically important fungal disease attacking olive in production countries. Here we reported the first highly contiguous whole genome sequence (46.08 Mb) of one isolate YUN35 of *V. oleagina*. The sequenced genome assembled into 61 contigs with N50 of 1.80 Mb, maximum contig length of 2.54 Mb, average contig length of 0.76 Mb, 11540 genes in total, annotated 9516, and 582 secreted, and at least 16 chromosomes. The secondary metabolic gene clusters were also identified and located in 13 regions within different genome contigs and compared to other venturia members. Phylogenetic analyses grouped *Venturia* members into two main groups; showing that *V. oleagina* is more genetically close to *V. inquilalis*, *V. aucuparia*, *V. nachicola*, and *V. pyrina* than the other venturia members. The secondary metabolism gene clusters detection using AntiSMASH fungal 4.0.0 software indicates that *V. oleaginea* has at least 14 clusters; most of these clusters belong to T1PKS and NPRS and can secret at least 80 chemical compounds. The described genome sequence and annotation resource will be useful sources for studying fungal biology, pathogen-host interaction, characterization of genes of interest, and population genetic diversity.

Chapter 4 Multi genes-based phylogenetic analysis of *Venturia oleaginea*, the causal agent of the olive leaf scab

4.1 Introduction:

Olive (*Olea europaea*. L) are among the most economically important fruit crops worldwide. Various pests and diseases cause threats to the olive [140]. Olive scab disease (OLS) has been the most fungus problematic for the growers in all growing countries. Typical olive scab symptoms show dark-colored circular spots, which are sometimes surrounded by a yellowish halo developed in the leaves' upper part, and diffused spots may appear on the leaf underside along the central vein [64]. *V.oleaginea* causes dieback of twigs and branches, reduction in leaf area, and high defoliation, leading to high yield losses [29].

The fungus *V. oleaginea* belongs to the genus *Venturia* Sacc. (Anamorph *Fusicladium* Bonord.) which includes pathogens that cause considerable economic damage to fruit crops worldwide [141] like *V. effuse*/ *Fusicladium effusum* G. Winter (1885) on Pecan (*Carya illinoensis*), *Venturia inaequalis*/*Fusicladium pomi* (Cooke) G. Winter (1875) on Apple (*Malus spp.*), *V. asperata* /*Fusicladium asperatum* Samuels & Sivan (1975) on *Malus spp.*, *Venturia pyrina*/ *Fusicladium pyrorum* Aderh. (1896) on European pear (*Pyrus communis* L.), *Venturia nashicola*/ *Fusicladium nashicola* S. Tanaka & S. Yamam. (1964) on Asian pear (*Pyrus pyrifolia*), *V. aucupariae* on Ash (*Sorbus* L.), *V. carpophila* / *Fusicladium carpophilum* E.E. Fisher (1961) on plum (*Prunus domestica* L./*Prunus dulcis*), *V. cerasi*/ *Fusicladium cerasi* Aderh. (1900) on sour cherry (*Prunus cerasus* L.) [142].

Although *V. oleaginea* has been reported for a long time [26], knowledge of this disease, especially at the molecular level, is still poor. In fact, this due to two main reasons, which are the inability of the disease to produce conidia, which are the only inoculum source known yet to cause the infection in the host [30], and the isolation time required to get a sufficient amount of mycelium for DNA extraction which reaches up to 6 months [29].

Few molecular studies have been conducted to study the pathogen at the molecular level concerning genetic variation and phylogenetic analysis [56-58, 60, 63]. A molecular PCR-based approach is widespread for studying and understanding microbial interaction, physiology, and

their evolutionary relationship. This approach uses short fragments of DNA sequences (nucleotides) that bind with the interested species' specific DNA sequences to amplify the targeted sequences [34]. The target sequences are highly conserved in different species and can be used as molecular markers (gene markers). Among these DNA conserved regions, the small subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (SSU), internal transcribed spacer (ITS), larger subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (LSU), and translation elongation factor-1 alpha (TEF1) [77, 78, 143].

González-Lamothe, Segura, Trapero, Baldoni, Botella and Valpuesta [60] described the DNA sequences of the 18s 5.8s and 28s rDNA genes (rDNA) and the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) regions of this fungus; their study was the first research conducted to identify *V. oleaginea* using molecular approaches (DNA primers). In the same study, they based on that the fungus belongs to the Dothideomycetes class as the *V. oleaginea* is imperfect fungi and will be located under the Deuteromycetes.

There are about 25,000 species that have been classified in the Deuteromycetes^[144]. Anyway, the classification of Deuteromycetes as ascomycetes or basidiomycetes is possible using molecular techniques. González-Lamothe, Segura, Trapero, Baldoni, Botella and Valpuesta [60] reported that *V. oleaginea* belongs to *Venturia* species with unknown sexual phase.

González-Lamothe, Segura, Trapero, Baldoni, Botella and Valpuesta [60] reported the *Venturia* species with the highest genetic similarity with *V. oleaginea*. Several new *Venturia* species have been announced, sequenced, and deposited in gene banks from then until now as well as *V. oleaginea* sequences to serve the genetic relations studies and phylogenetic analyses [56, 58, 59]. This chapter's main goal will include a wide range of available *V. oleaginea* sequences deposited in NCBI genebank and the same species sequences introduced in this study to conduct a wide phylogenetic analysis based on PCR molecular identification approach. The sequences presented here originated from two different geographic regions; one of them is considered a new evolution region for the olive's pathogen (China) and Palestine as the olive origin before distributed worldwide [12, 145]. As a result, we will know the closest species within the family and evaluation relations between species included in this analysis.

4.2 Material and method

4.2.1 Plant and fungal materials

Samples collection was carried out during May-June/2017-2018; the infected olive leaves from different cultivars with clear symptoms were collected from three provinces of China: Yunnan, Sichuan, Gansu, and infected olive leaves from Palestine (a Mediterranean country). Leaves were placed in envelopes and let dry at room temperature for 3 days, then stored at 4°C until required for isolation (Table 2-1).

4.2.2 Isolation and DNA extraction

To get pure isolates of *V. oleaginea*, the single spore isolation method was used. Spores were allowed to develop the germ tube firstly in Agar media for about 24-hour. Then, the germinated conidia transferred to new plates containing (OLCZ) medium for one month, then transferred and cultured in liquid PDB media (Guangdong Huaki Microbial Sci. And Tech. Co.Ltd.) for another 45 days. DNA from the obtained mycelia extracted using the CTAB method. (single spores isolation method and CTAB protocol were described earlier in chapter 2).

4.2.3 PCR and cloning conditions

Two pairs of primers from the small subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (SSU) region, one pair from the internal transcribed spacer (ITS), one pair from the partial larger subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA (LSU), and one pair from translation elongation factor-1 alpha (TEF1) were used in this study to amplify the DNA (Table 4-1).

Table 4- 1 List of PCR primers used for molecular classification.

表 4-1 用于分子分类的 PCR 引物列表。

Ribosomal gene region	Primer ID	Primer nucleotides sequence 5-3	AT	References
SSU	Species-specific F	(GCTTGTCTCAAGATTAAGCC)	55°C	[60]
	Species-specific R	(CCTTGTTACGACGACTTTTACTTCC)		
	NS1	(GTAGTCATATGCTTGTCTC)	55°C	[77]
	NS4	(CTCCGTCAATTCCTTTAAG)		
ITS	ITS4	(TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC)	50°C	[77]
	ITS5	(GGAAGTAAAAGTCGTAACAAGG)		
LSU	LROR	ACCCGCTGAACTTAAGC	55°C	[78]
	LR5	ATCCTGAGGGAACTTC		
EF (TEF1)	728F	CATCGAGAAGTTCGAGAAGG	55°C	[146, 147]
	EF-2	GGARGTACCAGTSATCATGTT		

PCR amplification was performed in the final volume of 50 μ l, including 45 μ l of A4 fidelity (1.1X) PCR mix (Gimmico Biotech Co., Ltd), 2 μ l of 10 μ M primer X 2 for each direction, and 1 μ l of DNA template (\approx 100ng/rxn). PCR thermal cycles adjusted as 5 min with 95 °C for initial denaturation, 35 cycles of (95 °C 40s for denaturing, primers annealing temperature for 40s, and 60s at 72°C for the extension) and finally one cycle of 72 °C for 10 minutes for the final extension. PCR products were sent for sequencing in (Zhejiang Youkang Biotechnology Co, Ltd).

4.2.4 Sequences used for phylogenetic analyses

In order to analyze the phylogenetic relations between species in different ribosomal gene regions, the table below shows the species that were selected:

Table 4-2 List of species included in the phylogenetic analyses.

表 4-2 纳入系统发育分析的物种清单。

Taxa name	accession numbers 18s region		
<i>Spilocaea oleagina</i>	AF338393.1	<i>Alternaria</i>	U05194.1
<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i>	KF766251.1	<i>alternata</i>	
<i>Helicoon fuscosporum</i>	AY856946.1	<i>Septoria nodorum</i>	U04236.1
<i>Tyrannosorus pinicola</i>	NG_070101.1	<i>Leptosphaeria maculans</i>	U04238.1
<i>Stomiopeltis sp.</i>	MG844148.1	<i>Westerdykella dispersa</i>	U42488.1
<i>Botryosphaeria sp.</i>	AB454225.1	<i>Sporormia lignicola (Preussia lignicola)</i>	U42478.1
<i>Trichodelitschia munkii</i>	DQ384070.1	<i>Dothidea insculpta</i>	U42474.1
<i>Neocatenulostroma microsporum</i>	GU214520.1	<i>Aureobasidium pullulans</i>	NG_062753.1
<i>Neocatenulostroma germanicum</i>	GU214518.1	<i>Sarcinomyces petricola</i>	Y18702.1
<i>Scleroconidioma sphagnicola</i>	AY220610.1	<i>Yeast (S.cerevisiae)</i>	J01353.1
<i>Ramoconidiophora euphorbiae</i>	NG_067663.1	<i>Botryosphaeria laricina</i>	KC509580.1
Taxa name	accession numbers ITS region		
<i>S.oleaginea</i>	AF338402.1,AF338400.1, AF338401.1	<i>D. insculpta</i>	KM388543.1
<i>F.oleagineum</i>	KF766166.1, EU035434.1	<i>A. pullulans</i>	FJ150904.1
<i>V.oleaginea</i>	MN038075.1	<i>S.petricola</i>	AJ244274.1
<i>A. alternata</i>	MN894080.1	<i>S.cerevisiae</i>	KC542799.1
<i>P.nodorum</i>	AF246946.1	<i>F.phillyreae</i>	EU035435.1
<i>L.maculans</i>	KT225526.1	<i>V. pyrina</i>	EU035469.1
<i>W. dispersa</i>	KM008551.1	<i>V. nashicola</i>	EU035465.1
<i>P. lignicola</i>	GQ203783.1	<i>V.tremulae</i>	EU035475.1

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<i>V. populina</i>	EU035467.1	<i>Fusicladium mandshuricum</i>	EU035433.1
		<i>V. catenospora</i>	NR 154470.1
Taxa name	accession numbers EF	region	
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	MN970210.1	<i>Parastagonospora nodorum</i>	LT797086.1
<i>Leptosphaeria maculans</i>	XM 003835085.1	<i>Cercospora beticola</i>	XM 023594009.1
<i>Preussia sp.</i>	LT797093.1	<i>Knufia petricola</i>	MT859426.1
<i>Gibbera conferta</i>	GU349041.1	<i>Pseudocercospora fijiensis</i>	XM 007922858.1
<i>Paramycoleptodiscus albizziae</i>	MK495979.1	<i>Aureobasidium pullulans</i>	EU719388.1
<i>Yeast (S.cerevisiae)</i>	M10992.1	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i>	GU349089.1 GU349023.1 GU456288.1 KX525667.1 GU349022.1
Taxa name	accession numbers SSU		
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	MK757635.1	<i>Phaeosphaeria nodorum</i>	AF164372.1
<i>Leptosphaeria maculans</i>	AY857734.1	<i>Westerdykella dispersa</i>	DQ384085.1
<i>Sporormia lignicola (Preussia lignicola)</i>	MW131830.1	<i>Dothidea insculpta</i>	DQ247810.1
<i>Aureobasidium pullulans</i>	JX188092.1	<i>Sarcinomyces petricola</i>	FJ225753.1
<i>Yeast (S.cerevisiae)</i>	AF459095.1	Uncultured <i>Pezizomycotina</i>	EU647053.1
<i>Venturia inaequalis</i>	EF114737.1	<i>Venturia pyrina</i>	EF114739.1

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<i>Spilocaea oleagina</i>	AF3383931	<i>Fusicladium convolvularum</i>	AY251124.1
<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i>	KF766251.1		
<i>Venturia oleaginea</i>	MK843251.1	<i>Venturia asperata</i>	EF114736.1
Taxa name	accession numbers LSU		
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	MN202778.1	<i>L. maculans</i>	AY849946.1
<i>Phaeosphaeria nodorum</i>	GU456332.1	<i>Sporormia lignicola</i> (<i>Preussia lignicola</i>)	DQ384098.1
<i>Westerdykella dispersa</i>	MH869665.1	<i>Dothidea insculpta</i>	MH869284.1
<i>Aureobasidium pullulans</i>	JN938892.1	Yeast (<i>S.cerevisiae</i>)	GU938193.1
<i>Sarcinomyces petricola</i>	FJI76893.1	<i>Venturia nashicola</i>	MT845770.1
<i>Venturia hanliniana</i>	AF050290.1	<i>Venturia chlorospora</i>	DQ384101.1
<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i>	KF766331.1, AF338397.1, MK810879.1, MK810878.1,	<i>Fusicladium peltigericola</i>	HQ599579.2
<i>Venturia oleaginea</i>	MK810877.1		
<i>Venturia pyrina</i>	MH870232.1	<i>Venturia paralias</i>	MN864538.1

The selection criteria were to select the 10 closest different species obtained after running the NCBI blast tool. Also, the sequences of species that were used in González-Lamothe, Segura, Trapero, Baldoni, Botella and Valpuesta ^[60] are included; these sequences were used in the analysis of the 18s sequences in his study. In this Chapter, the same or close ones were used to analyze different sequences in each region. The unshown *V. oleaginea* species in the NCBI screen blast results were searched and added for analysis except for the sequences of elongation factor gene region, which were found cloned with different primers other than used in this study.

4.2.5 Sequences analysis

The obtained *V. oleaginea* sequences for the isolates introduced in this study were edited and aligned with SnapGene software (GSL Biotech LLC, Chicago, IL, USA). Consensus sequences were created and used to get the closest species of our population sequences by

running the NCBI blast tool for each gene region. Later all the sequences were aligned using Pro-Coffee Aligns homologous promoter regions web tool ^[148]. Evolutionary analyses were conducted using MEGA X ^[80]. Phylogenetic trees were calculated by the neighbor-Joining method ^[81]. Bootstrap analysis was performed 1000 times to confirm the produced trees' reliability ^[82], and The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter method ^[83]. *Saccharomyces* sp. partial sequences of 18S, ITS, LSU, SSU, and elongation factor-1 alpha (TEF1) regions (*J01353.1*, *KC542799.1*, *GU938193.1*, *FJ225753.1*, *M10992.1*), respectively, were used as outgroup in each tree. Consensus sequences for each gene region also included in the constructed trees.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Morphological Features of *V.oleaginea* isolates

The morphological features of the obtained isolates were described in detail in chapter 2 of this study. Briefly, the obtained colonies are circular-convex colonies with a dark greenish olivaceous surface that become brownish in older colonies and back is dark. It looks like a hemispherical body with surrounding-irregular halo margins that appeared clearly in OL and PDA media photo (Figure 4-1).

Figure 4-1 Morphological characters of *Venturia oleaginea* isolate. Isolation was carried out using the single-spore isolation method in (OLCZ1:1) medium, then subcultured in PDA medium.

图 4-1 *Venturia oleaginea* 分离菌的形态特征。采用单孢分离法在 (OLCZ1:1) 培养基中进行分离，然后在 PDA 培养基中进行亚培养。

4.3.2 Sequences analyses

After sequencing, the numbers of obtained sequences used in this study are 78, 79, 77, 77, 81 for the 18S, LSU, SSU, ITS, and EF (TEF1) regions, respectively. BLASTn results reveal high similarity with other *V. oleaginea* sequences from other different areas. The following figures showing the closest species blast alignment results versus the consensus sequences in each region:

Download ▾ GenBank Graphics

Venturia inaequalis strain KEL_204_1 translation elongation factor 1-alpha
 Sequence ID: **KX525667.1** Length: 949 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 24 to 948 GenBank Graphics ▾ Next Match ▲

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
1465 bits(793)	0.0	881/925(95%)	0/925(0%)	Plus/Plus
Query 1	CCCAGGCCGATTGCGCCATTCTCATCATTGCCGCCGGCACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTA	60		
Sbjct 24	CCCAGGCTGATTGCGCCATTCTCATCATTGCCGCTGGTACTGGTGAGTTCGAGGCTGGTA	83		
Query 61	TCTCCAAGGATGGTCAGACTCGTGAGCACGCTCTGCTCGCCTACACCTTGGGTGTCAAGC	120		
Sbjct 84	TCTCCAAGGATGGTCAGACTCGTGAGCACGCCCTGCTCGCCTACACCTTGGGTGTCAAGC	143		
Query 121	AGCTCATCGTTGCCATCAACAAGATGGACACCACCAAGTGGTCCGAGGAGCGATTCAACG	180		
Sbjct 144	AGCTCATCGTCGCCATCAACAAGATGGACACCACCAAGTGGTCCGAGGAGCGATTCAACG	203		
Query 181	AAATTATCAAGGAGACCTCTTCTTCATCAAGAAGGTCGTTACAACCCAAAGCACGTCC	240		
Sbjct 204	AAATCATCAAGGAGACATCTCTTCATCAAGAAGGTTGGTTACAACCCAAAGCACGTCC	263		
Query 241	CATTCGTGCCAATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGCGACAACATGATCGATAACTCCACCAACTGCC	300		
Sbjct 264	CATTCGTGCCAATCTCCGGTTTCAACGGTGACAACATGATCGACAACCTCCAGCAACTGCC	323		
Query 301	CATGGTACAAGGGCTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGTCCAAGGTCACCGGAAAGACCTCCTCG	360		
Sbjct 324	CATGGTACAAGGGTTGGGAGAAGGAGACCAAGTCCAAGGTCACCGGAAAGACCTCCTCG	383		
Query 361	AGGCCATTGATGCCATCGACCCACCATCCCGTCCATCCGACAAGCCTCTCCGTCTTCTCTC	420		
Sbjct 384	AGGCCATTGATGCCATCGACCCACCATCCCGTCCATCCGACAAGCCTCTCCGTCTTCTCTC	443		
Query 421	TCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATCGGAACAGTGCCAGTCGGTCGTGTGAGACCG	480		
Sbjct 444	TCCAGGATGTCTACAAGATCGGTGGTATTGGAACAGTGCCAGTCGGTCGTGTGAGACCG	503		
Query 481	GTGTCATCAAGGCCGGTATGGTCGTACCTTCGCCCCAGCTGGTGTCAACCACCGAAGTCA	540		
Sbjct 504	GTGTCATCAAGGCCGGTATGGTCGTACCTTCGCCCCAGCTGGTGTCAACCACCGAAGTCA	563		
Query 541	AGTCCGTCGAGATGCACCACGAGCAGCTCACCAGGGGTCTCCAGGTGACAACGTCGGAT	600		
Sbjct 564	AGTCCGTCGAGATGCACCACGAGCAGCTCGTTGAGGGTCTCCAGGTGACAACGTCGGAT	623		
Query 601	TCAACGTCAAGAACGTCCTCCGTAAAGGAAATTGCGCCGTGGTAAACGTCGCTGGTGACTCCA	660		
Sbjct 624	TCAACGTCAAGAACGTTTCCGTCAAGGAAATTGCTCGTGGTAAACGTCGCCGGTGACTCCA	683		
Query 661	AGAACGACCCCTCAAAGGGTGTGAGTCTTCAACGCCCAAGGTATCGTCTCTCAACCACC	720		
Sbjct 684	AGAACGACCCCTCAAAGGGTGCAGTCTTCAACGCCCAAGGTATCGTCTCTCAACCACC	743		
Query 721	CAGGTCAAGTTGGTGTGTTATGCTCCAGTTTGGACTGCCACACTGCCACATTGCCT	780		
Sbjct 744	CAGGTCAAGTCCGTTGCTGTTACGCTCCAGTCTTGGATTGCCACACTGCCACATTGCTT	803		
Query 781	GCAAGTTCGCTGAGCTTTTGGAGAAGATTGATCGCCGTAAGTAAATCCAAGTAAATCTT	840		
Sbjct 804	GCAAGTTCGCTGAGCTTTTGGAGAAGATCGATCGCCGTAAGTAAAGCCACCGAAACCA	863		
Query 841	CTCCCAAGTTCATCAAGTCTGGGGACGCCGCCATCGTCAAGATGATTCCCTCCAAGCCAA	900		
Sbjct 864	GCCCCAAGTTCATCAAGTCTGGTGACGCCGCCATTGTCAAGATGATTCTTCCAAGCCAA	923		
Query 901	TGTGCGTTGAGGCCTTCACTGACTA	925		
Sbjct 924	TGTGCGTTGAGGCCTTCACTGACTA	948		

Figure 4-2 BLASTn similarity of the sequence identity of *Venturia oleaginea* sequenced with EF1-728R & EF-2 blast against *V. inaequalis* KX525667.1, identity 95%.

图 4-2 BLASTn 的结果显示 *Venturia oleaginea* (使用 EF1-728R 和 EF-2 序列) 和 *V. inaequalis* KX525667.1 之间具有 95% 的一致性。

Figure 4-3 BLASTn similarity of the sequence identity of *Venturia oleaginea* sequenced with 18s primers, blast against *F. oleagineum* KF766166.1. Identity 99%.

图 4-3 BLASTn 的结果显示 *Venturia oleaginea* (使用 18s 序列) 和 *F. oleagineum* KF766166.1 之间具有 99% 的一致性。

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Venturia oleaginea strain Cam1 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial ribosomal RNA gene, complete sequence; and internal transcribed spacer
 Sequence ID: [MN038075.1](#) Length: 488 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 1 to 488 GenBank Graphics ▼ Next Match ▲

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
902 bits(488)	0.0	488/488(100%)	0/488(0%)	Plus/Plus
Query 35	GAACCTGCGGAAGGATCATTAAATGGGGCCAGCCTCCGGGCGCACCCCCACCCTTTGTAACC	94		
Sbjct 1	GAACCTGCGGAAGGATCATTAAATGGGGCCAGCCTCCGGGCGCACCCCCACCCTTTGTAACC	60		
Query 95	GCGGCCCGGATTGCGGCCCGGGGAGTAACCCCCGTTTCGCGGGGGGGCCCCGCTGC	154		
Sbjct 61	GCGGCCCGGATTGCGGCCCGGGGAGTAACCCCCGTTTCGCGGGGGGGCCCCGCTGC	120		
Query 155	CGGAATTAGCCAACCCTGCCTTGAAAAGTGAAGTCTGAGAACGAGTCAAATCGAACAAAA	214		
Sbjct 121	CGGAATTAGCCAACCCTGCCTTGAAAAGTGAAGTCTGAGAACGAGTCAAATCGAACAAAA	180		
Query 215	CTTTCAACAACGGATCTCTTGTTCTGGCAACGATGAAGAACGCAGCGAAATGCGATAAG	274		
Sbjct 181	CTTTCAACAACGGATCTCTTGTTCTGGCAACGATGAAGAACGCAGCGAAATGCGATAAG	240		
Query 275	TAATGTGAATTGCAGAATTCAGTGAATCATCGAATCTTTGAACGCACATTGCGCCCCCTG	334		
Sbjct 241	TAATGTGAATTGCAGAATTCAGTGAATCATCGAATCTTTGAACGCACATTGCGCCCCCTG	300		
Query 335	GTATTCCGGGGGGCACACCTGTTTCGAGCGCCATTTCTACCCTGGAGCCCTGCTCTGTGAT	394		
Sbjct 301	GTATTCCGGGGGGCACACCTGTTTCGAGCGCCATTTCTACCCTGGAGCCCTGCTCTGTGAT	360		
Query 395	GGGCCCCGTCTCGCGGACGGGCCGAAACCCGTGGGCGCCGTCGTCCGGCCCCGAGCGT	454		
Sbjct 361	GGGCCCCGTCTCGCGGACGGGCCGAAACCCGTGGGCGCCGTCGTCCGGCCCCGAGCGT	420		
Query 455	AGCAAGAGAAATCCCTCGCTCGGAGCGCCTGGCGGCGGCGCCCCGAAACCTACTTCTA	514		
Sbjct 421	AGCAAGAGAAATCCCTCGCTCGGAGCGCCTGGCGGCGGCGCCCCGAAACCTACTTCTA	480		
Query 515	CAAGGTTG 522			
Sbjct 481	CAAGGTTG 488			

Figure 4-4 BLASTn similarity of the sequence identity of *V. oleaginea* sequenced with NS1 & NS4 primers ,blast against *Venturia oleaginea* MN038075.1. Identity 100%.

图 4-4 用 NS1 和 NS4 引物对 *Venturia oleaginea* 进行序列相似性分析, 对 *V. oleaginea* MN038075.1 进行搜索, 一致度 100%。

Figure 4-5 BLASTn similarity of the sequence identity of *Venturia oleaginea* sequenced with ITS4 & ITS5 primers, blast against *Venturia oleaginea* MK84323501. Identity 100%.

图 4-5 BLASTn 的结果显示 *Venturia oleaginea* (使用 ITS4 和 ITS5 序列) 和 *Venturia oleaginea* MK84323501 之间具有 100% 的一致性。

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Fusicladium oleagineum strain CBS 113427 culture-collection CBS:113427
Sequence ID: [KF766331.1](#) Length: 884 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 1 to 883 [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#) ▼ Next Match ▲

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
1626 bits(880)	0.0	882/883(99%)	0/883(0%)	Plus/Plus
Query 13	AGCATATCAATAAGCGGAGGAAAAGAAACCAACAGGGATTGCCTCAGTAACGGCGAGTGA			72
Sbjct 1	AGCATATCAATAAGCGGAGGAAAAGAAACCAACAGGGATTGCCTCAGTAACGGCGAGTGA			60
Query 73	AGCGGCAACAGCTCAAATTTGAAATCTGGCGCAAGCCCGAGTTGTAATTTGCAGAGGATG			132
Sbjct 61	AGCGGCAACAGCTCAAATTTGAAATCTGGCGCAAGCCCGAGTTGTAATTTGCAGAGGATG			120
Query 133	TTTCGGGTGAAGCCACGGTCCAAGTCCCTTGGAACAGGACGTCATAGAGGGTGAGAACCC			192
Sbjct 121	TTTCGGGTGAAGCCACGGTCCAAGTCCCTTGGAACAGGACGTCATAGAGGGTGAGAACCC			180
Query 193	CGTACCTGGCCGTCGGTGCCCCCGCTGTGAAACTCCTTCGACGAGTCGAGTTGTTTGGG			252
Sbjct 181	CGTACCTGGCCGTCGGTGCCCCCGCTGTGAAACTCCTTCGACGAGTCGAGTTGTTTGGG			240
Query 253	AATGCAGCTCTAAATTGGTGGTAAATTCATCTAAAGCTAAATACCGCCAGAGACCGAT			312
Sbjct 241	AATGCAGCTCTAAATTGGTGGTAAATTCATCCAAAGCTAAATACCGCCAGAGACCGAT			300
Query 313	AGCGCACAAAGTAGAGTGATCGAAAGATGAAAAGCACTTTGAAAAGAGAGTTAAAAAGTAC			372
Sbjct 301	AGCGCACAAAGTAGAGTGATCGAAAGATGAAAAGCACTTTGAAAAGAGAGTTAAAAAGTAC			360
Query 373	GTGAAATTGTTGAAAGGGAAGCGCTTGCAGCCAGACTTGCCCGCGGTTGCTCAGCCCGCC			432
Sbjct 361	GTGAAATTGTTGAAAGGGAAGCGCTTGCAGCCAGACTTGCCCGCGGTTGCTCAGCCCGCC			420
Query 433	CTTTGGCGGGTGCACCTCTCCGCGGTGAGCCAGCATCGGTTTGGGCGGCCGGATAAAGG			492
Sbjct 421	CTTTGGCGGGTGCACCTCTCCGCGGTGAGCCAGCATCGGTTTGGGCGGCCGGATAAAGG			480
Query 493	CGTTGGGAACGTAGCCTCCCCCTCGGGGAGGTGTTATAGCCCGGCGCGCAATGCGACCAGC			552
Sbjct 481	CGTTGGGAACGTAGCCTCCCCCTCGGGGAGGTGTTATAGCCCGGCGCGCAATGCGACCAGC			540
Query 553	CCGGACCGAGGTTTCGCGCTCTGCTAGGATGCTGGCGTAATGGCCGTAAGCGGCCCGTCTT			612
Sbjct 541	CCGGACCGAGGTTTCGCGCTCTGCTAGGATGCTGGCGTAATGGCCGTAAGCGGCCCGTCTT			600
Query 613	GAAACACGGACCAAGGAGTCTAACATCTATGCGAGTGTGTTGGGTGTCAAACCCGTGCGCG			672
Sbjct 601	GAAACACGGACCAAGGAGTCTAACATCTATGCGAGTGTGTTGGGTGTCAAACCCGTGCGCG			660
Query 673	TAATGAAAGTGAACGGAGGTGGGAACCGCAAGGTGCACCATCGACCGATCCTGATGTCTT			732
Sbjct 661	TAATGAAAGTGAACGGAGGTGGGAACCGCAAGGTGCACCATCGACCGATCCTGATGTCTT			720
Query 733	CGGAAGGATTTGAGTAAGAGCATAGCTGTTGGGACCCGAAAGATGGTGAACATATGCGTGA			792
Sbjct 721	CGGAAGGATTTGAGTAAGAGCATAGCTGTTGGGACCCGAAAGATGGTGAACATATGCGTGA			780
Query 793	ATAGGGTGAAGCCAGAGGAAACTCTGGTGGAGGCTCGCAGCGGTTCTGACGTGCAAATCG			852
Sbjct 781	ATAGGGTGAAGCCAGAGGAAACTCTGGTGGAGGCTCGCAGCGGTTCTGACGTGCAAATCG			840
Query 853	ATCGTCAAATTTGCGTATAGGGGCGAAAGACTAATCGAACCAT		895	
Sbjct 841	ATCGTCAAATTTGCGTATAGGGGCGAAAGACTAATCGAACCAT		883	

Figure 4-6 BLASTn similarity of the sequence identity of *Venturia oleaginea* sequenced with LSU. Blast against *F. oleagineum* KF766331.1. Identity 99%.

图 4-6 BLASTn 的结果显示 *Venturia oleaginea* (使用 LSU 序列) 和 *oleagineum* KF766331.1., 之间具有 99% 的一致性。

4.3.3 Evolutionary relationships of taxa

The constructed phylogenetic tree with 18S sequences revealed that all *V. oleaginea* sequences shared one common ancestor belonging to the Venturiaceae family *Tyrannosorus pinicola* (NG-070101.1) and formed one main cluster (clade), which divided to form sisters clades or subclades. In other constructed trees, *V. oleaginea* sequences shared *Fusicladium convolvularum* (AY251124.1), *Venturia inaequalis*, *Fusicladium phillyreae* (EU035435.1), as common ancestors in SSU, EF, and ITS respectively, and shared three ancestors in LSU based tree (*Venturia paralias* (MN864538.1), *Venturia nashicola* (MT845770.1), *Venturia pyrina* (MH870232.1). All *V. oleaginea* sequences grouped with other Venturiaceae members in one main clade with high supporting values (bootstrap) LSU, SSU, ITS, EF, and 18S 99%, 66%, 92%, 99%, and 81%, respectively (Figures 4-7,8,9,11, 12).

Figure 4- 7 Neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree of *Venturia oleagina* strains and homologs from same species and others dothideomycetes based on 18S sequences. The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter model with 1,000 bootstrap replicates.

图 4-7 基于 18S 序列，构建了 *Venturia oleagina* 菌株及其同系物与其它座囊菌亚纲菌物的邻接系统发育树。用 Tamura 3-parameter 模型计算 1000 bootstrap 重复的进化距离。

Figure 4-8 Neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree of *Venturia oleaginea* strains and homologs from same species and others dothideomycetes based on SSU sequences. The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter model with 1,000 bootstrap replicates.

图 4-8 基于 SSU 序列，构建了 *Venturia oleaginea* 菌株及其同系物与其它座囊菌亚纲菌物的邻接系统发育树。用 Tamura 3-parameter 模型计算 1000 bootstrap 重复的进化距离。

Figure 4-9 Neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree of *Venturia oleaginea* strains and homologs from same species and others dothideomycetes based on LSU sequences. The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter model with 1,000 bootstrap replicates.

图 4-9 基于 LSU 序列，构建了 *Venturia oleaginea* 菌株及其同系物与其它座囊菌亚纲菌物的邻接系统发育树。用 Tamura 3-parameter 模型计算 1000 bootstrap 重复的进化距离。

Figure 4-10 Neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree of *Venturia oleaginea* strains and homologs from same species and others dothideomycetes based on EF sequences. The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter model with 1,000 bootstrap replicates.

图 4-10 基于 EF 序列，构建了 *Venturia oleaginea* 菌株及其同系物与其它座囊菌亚纲菌物的邻接系统发育树。用 Tamura 3-parameter 模型计算 1000 bootstrap 重复的进化距离。

Figure 4- 11 Neighbor-joining phylogenetic tree of *Venturia oleaginea* strains and homologs from same species and others dothideomycetes based on ITS sequences. The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter model with 1,000 bootstrap replicates.

图 4-11 基于 ITS 序列，构建了 *Venturia oleaginea* 菌株及其同系物与其它座囊菌亚纲菌物的邻接系统发育树。用 Tamura 3-parameter 模型计算 1000 bootstrap 重复的进化距离。

Other phylogenetic analyses were conducted to improve the bootstrap values in SSU and 18s trees. The analyses included the sequences obtained after blast against *V. oleaginea* consensus in both gene regions; the included sequences were only venturiaceae members in SSU, while the blast gave us only two venturiaceae members sequenced with 18s genes and others appeared in the tree, are the species with high similarities to *V. oleaginea*. *Alternaria alternate* sequences (U05194.1) MK757635.1 were used as an outgroup in both trees. In both new trees. *V. oleaginea* strains introduced in this study or the already deposited in NCBI were grouped in a robust clade with 99% bootstrap values (Figure 4-12/13).

Figure 4-12 Phylogenetic tree constructed based on SSU sequences. (*Venturia* spp. and *Venturia oleaginea* deposited in NCBI) were included. The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter model with 1,000 bootstrap replicates.

图 4-12 基于 SSU 序列构建的系统发育树。(包含 NCBI 中的 *Venturia* 和 *Venturia oleaginea*)。用 Tamura 3-parameter 模型计算 1000 bootstrap 重复的进化距离。

Figure 4-13 Phylogenetic tree constructed based on 18S sequences. (closest species. and *Venturia oleaginea* deposited in NCBI) were included. The evolutionary distances were computed using Tamura 3-parameter model with 1,000 bootstrap replicates.

图 4-13 基于 18S 序列构建的系统进化树。（包含 NCBI 中 *Venturia oleaginea* 近缘物种）。用 Tamura 3-parameter 模型计算 1000 bootstrap 重复的进化距离。

V. oleaginea isolates showed a close relationship with others *V.oleaginea* sequences obtained from NCBI Genbank in all trees. Identities reach 100% in some cases, as shown in previous blast tables results. The identity percentage of the *V. oleaginea* strains and isolates DNA sequences introduced in this study were 99.9%, 99.15%, 97.97% (only *V. oleaginea* sequences introduced in this study), 99.8%,99.32% for SSU, LSU, EF, ITS, and 18s respectively.

The distances between nucleotide sequences are summarized using PCA dendrogram based on the distance matrix extracted for each phylogenetic analysis, which directly hits the nucleotides in the same positions of aligned sequences. The PCA analysis was carried out using Jalview software ^[149] in which pairwise alignment was conducted for the *V.oleaginea* sequences and percentage identity was calculated.

Figure 4-14 PCA scatter plots of DNA sequences; the plots refer to sequences in (A) SSU, (B) LSU, (C) EF, (D) 18S, and (E) ITS regions. The sequences included in this analysis are the *Venturia oleaginea* isolates included in this study and other *V. oleaginea* strains with accession numbers from different regions. The horizontal yellow line refers to X-axis, the vertical yellow line is the Y-axis, and the left inclined yellow line the Z-axis.

图 4-14 DNA 序列的 PCA 散点图；该图指的是 (A) SSU、(B) LSU、(C) EF、(D) 18S 和 (E) ITS 区域的序列。该分析中包括的序列是本研究中包括的 *Venturia oleaginea* 分离物和其他来自不同地区的 *V. oleaginea* 菌株的登录号。水平黄线指的是 X 轴，垂直黄线是 Y 轴，左边的倾斜黄线是 Z 轴。

The least dispersion of the sequences was in the SSU and ITS regions, where the PCA draw one cloud of sequences in both analyses with two to four anomalous sequences (Figure 4-14 A & E). While the other plots present more of the anomalous sequences and the higher was found in 18S region. Sequences cloned with LR0R, and LR5 primers (LSU region) showed a rectangular cloud containing most of the sequences, four of five sequences obtained from the gene bank were located outside this cloud (Figure 4-14 B).

4.4 Discussion

In this Chapter, new *V.oleaginea* strains from China and Palestine, which were introduced in this study, and others obtained from previous studies were analyzed to find the same species' phylogenetic relations. Other sequences belonging to the Dothideomycetes class were also included in the analysis.

The findings of this chapter are in line with previous studies conducted with the same aim and exception that we included more numbers of same species sequences. The new venturiaceae sequences deposited in the NCBI genebank after the previous studies give us a clearer idea about the closest species for the *V. oleaginea* strains. The phylogenetic analyses conducted in this study and other analyses like the NCBI blasting tool and ID percentage of the sequences and Principal Component Analysis (PCA); revealed the high similarities between *V. oleaginea* strains from different regions. Anyway, the study of the phylogenetic relations based on partial sequences of the interested genes regions is a good approach to study the genetic relations between sequences of different strains, but still limited and other genotypes-based PCR approaches studies like using Intersimple Sequence Repeat Markers (ISSR) or universal microsatellite SSR, Box REPAIR primers ^[59], etc., are required to get more information on this fungus genetic diversity. Such studies will help determine the geographic correlation with different fungus populations ^[91]. The identity percentage between *Venturia oleaginea* sequences revealed high similarity between all strains, noting that the lowest percentage was found within sequences cloned with LSU and 18s regions.

4.5 Conclusion

Venturia oleaginea is a filamentous fungus belonging to Dothideomycetes class and a member of the venturiaceae family. The phylogenetic study based on five different gene regions (LSU, SSU, ITS, 18S, and EF (TEF1)) revealed the high similarities between the same species. *V.oleaginea* strains from other countries are also grouped within the same main clades produced in different phylogenetic-analyses. Dothideomycetes species included in the analyses are grouped into different clades in all constructed trees. Percentage of identity between *V. oleaginea* were 99.9%, 99.15%, 97.97%, 99.8%, 99.32% % in SSU, LSU, EF, ITS, and 18S, respectively. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) clustered the *V. oleaginea* strains close to each other (one genetic cloud), indicating a common ancestry and relatedness to the same genetic pool.

Chapter 5 Summary, innovation, and recommendations

5.1 Summary

This thesis includes valuable epidemiological studies related to olive leaf scab disease. In the first part of the introduction chapter, we reviewed the global importance of olive as it's occupying the third place within the most cultivated fruit trees worldwide, most important growing areas, and global production volume of olives, in addition to a brief introduction about the olive situation in China as a new producer, and the three leading growing regions, production and imported quantities of olive oil and expected cultivation areas in the near future. In the second part of the introduction chapter, we briefly reviewed the most important diseases that affect olives, the most important of which is olive scab disease. In this part, we reviewed the common pathogen names, the causal agent, areas of incidence worldwide, favorable conditions, and infection process, and summarized some facts about the pathogen extracted by reviewing all of the available information resources. *V. oleaginea* is very hard to deal with in the laboratory, not easy to isolate and needs a long time in the isolation process. Furthermore, *Venturia oleaginea* isolates cannot produce conidia, which is the only know source inoculum to infect the host plant.

Therefore, it was necessary to find a good and fast way to isolate this disease from the host plant, and since the pathogen, when isolated, loses the ability to produce the spores necessary to cause infection in the host plant, it was necessary to find a way to stimulate the fungus to produce these spores to cause infection in the plant.

In the next chapter (chapter two), we examined two methods for isolating fungi. The first method results, which is isolating the pathogen from plant tissues, particularly from infected leaves, were disappointing. About 200 isolates of plant tissues were prepared during the two isolation sessions, and the percentage of obtaining pure isolates was zero regardless of the sterilization method. The other isolation method, which is isolation from the single spore, showed excellent results when we isolated the fungus in a new innovative media, consisting of olive leaf extract in addition to Czapek media -which mainly includes mineral salts components-. Our success rate percentage in obtaining pure isolates was about 48%, and it's a very high percentage since the mentioned method lacks ideal sterilization standards.

On the other side, the growth rate of the fungus was tested using different growth media, and the best results were obtained when the fungus was grown on PDA and PDB media; the most important thing that can be summarized in the fungus isolation method is that the fungus needs a weak media consisting of olive leaf extract rich in mineral salts, this media is suitable for isolating the *V. oleaginea*, but it is not suitable for the growth of other strange fungi under low temperature. In the Isolation media, the fungus will form an initial tiny colony about 20 days after isolation, then transferred to grow in rich media (PDA) to enhance the growth. In such a way, we will get a good amount of fungal material in about 2 months instead of the long time reported by others extending to 6 months. In the second chapter, we reviewed some of the methods used to stimulate conidiation in different fungi. We have succeeded in stimulating *V. oleaginea* for the production of conidia by culturing it in pine needles-based media and exposing it at the same time to UV radiation. The conidia induction method we used enabled us to obtain conidia for the first time in good quantities in vitro, allowing us to carry out a successful inoculation and infection of the host plant.

In the third chapter of the thesis, the complete genome of the fungus that we published is presented, where the features of this genome were explored and compared its features to other genomes from the *Venturia* members, and a phylogenetic tree was made within the same family based on the published genomes.

The most important thing in this chapter is the genes annotation, as the published genome of 46.08 MB includes about 11540 genes, of which about 9516 are annotated. The genetic relationship between *V. oleaginea* and other *Venturia* family members was also studied based on published genomes. Founding that *V. oleaginea* is approximately the same size as the *V. effusa*, the causal agent of pecan scab and genetically close to *V. inquilalis*, *V. aucupariae*, *V. nachicola*, and *V. pyrina*. 14 secondary metabolism gene clusters have been discovered which synthesis or are involved in the synthesis of about 80 non-replicating chemical compounds.

In the fourth chapter, a wide phylogenetic study of the fungus *V. oleaginea* was carried out, through which approximately 400 same species sequences were included. The genetic materials for them were isolated from sixty-eight isolates from the Chinese regions and twenty isolates from Palestinian areas and cloned with five pairs of molecular primers belonging to 4 gene regions. Also, Dothideomycetes class sequences, most *Venturia* members and sequences of

the same species (*V. oleaginea*) obtained from NCBI were included. The study results revealed that the different *V. oleaginea* communities, whether they were presented in this study or those obtained through NCBI from other regions, are genetically very close. The percentage of identity was more than 99% in all the analyses made and based on different gene regions, indicating that *V. oleaginea* populations share common ancestry and relatedness to the same genetic pool.

5.2 Innovation

We firstly suggested a good protocol to isolate *V. oleaginea* from the infected olive leaves in which the interested researchers can obtain a good quantity of the fungus genetic material in about 2 months to conduct their different experiments instead of long time reported by others.

This study suggested the first method to induce *V. oleaginea* isolates to produce conidia. Consequently, this method will help the researchers study the plant-pathogen interactions such as gene expressions. In addition, The first plant inoculation using conidia produced *in-vitro* was carried out.

During this study, the first genome of the *V. oleaginea* was sequenced and deposited as a master record in National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) and published in Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions Journal (MPMI).

During this study, phylogeny analyzes were performed for the first time based on the published genome of this pathogen and thus genetic relation within *Venturia* species. Also, phylogenetic analyses were performed based on a wide range of the same species sequences. High identical percentages were found between *venturia oleaginea* species, which indicates the asexual cloning used by the pathogen in reproduction.

5.3 Recommendation and future prospects

Olives are a promising agricultural production sector in China, and cultivated areas are steadily increasing, as is the case with the increasing demand for olive oil. Olive leaf scab disease is considered a real threat to this sector. This study can be used greatly to manage this disease and learn more of its secrets. Accordingly, the information this thesis contained should be used to conduct further studies on this disease. The published genome is an important source of information for further analysis, like defining virulence-associated genes, and pathogen

effector repertoires, and host defense systems, particularly in the context of the Cytoplasmic effectors (CEs), PAMP triggered immunity (PTI), and effector-triggered immunity (ETI) model.

This study will also be an incentive to go into the study of this fungus away from concerns about the isolation process's time and success, and it will also be an incentive for those concerned who wish to identify some target genes through molecular Koch's postulates test.

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Published papers and other Academic Achievements during the Program

1. Published paper

1st Author "Genome Sequence of *Venturia oleaginea*, the Causal Agent of Olive Leaf Scab." *Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions* 33, no. 9 (2020): 1095-1097.

2. Submitted paper

- 1- 5th The association of ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae) with fungi: a 200-year review. Submitted on 2020.12.15 to "nature scientific data" (**waiting final decision**).
- 2- Assessment of Genetic Diversity in Ancient and Modern Olive *Olea europaea* L. Varieties in Palestine accepted on 2021.4.17. *Int. J. Agric. Sci.*, (in technical reviewing).
- 3- Isolation, identification, and sporulation induction of *Venturia oleagina*, the causal agent of olive leaf scab. under reviewing

3. Posters

Isolation, identification and sporulation induction of *Venturia oleaginea*, the causal agent of olive leaf scab. 3rd *Annual Conference of Belt and Road/South-South Cooperation Agricultural Education, Science and Technology Innovation League (BRSSCAL)*. Sanya-Hainan Province-China. P 74 (abstract).

4. Presentations

Speaker "Isolation, identification and sporulation induction of *Venturia oleaginea*, the causal agent of olive leaf scab". *Global Reach: Solving Agriculture Problems through research and innovation*. Dalhousie Faculty of Agriculture (virtual event).

Appendices

Supplementary Tables

S1 (A, B). Total numbers of obtained isolates using two isolation methods.

(A)

Growing media/	Total No.of isolates prepared from infected leaves and sterilized with HgCl ₂ 0.1 % + Ethanol 70%.	Contaminations Occurred %	Total No.of isolates prepared from infected leaves and sterilized with Ethanol 70%.	Contaminations Occurred %	Total contamination%	Obtained Pure Isolates
Session 1						
PDA	25	6	25	13	19	0
OL	25	3	25	3	6	0
OLCZ1:1	25	3	25	4	7	0
CZ	25	3	25	4	7	0
Total/ %	100	0.15	100	0.24	0.195	0
Session 2						
PDA	25	6	25	11	17	0
OL	25	2	25	5	7	0
OLCZ1:1	25	2	25	4	6	0
CZ	25	1	25	2	3	0
Total/ %	100	0.11	100	0.22	0.165	0

(B)

Growing media	No. of isolates with spore isolation method	Isolates obtained	2nd session	Isolates obtained	3rd session	Isolates obtained	4th session	Isolates obtained	total	average

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	1st session									
PDA	25	1	25	0	25	2	25	2	5	0.05
OL	25	6	25	10	25	8	25	7	31	0.31
OLCZ1: 1	25	11	25	13	25	15	25	9	48	0.48
CZ	25	2	25	3	25	4	25	2	11	0.11
Total/ %	100	20	100	26	100	29	100	20	95	0.2375

S2. BLASTn results of Isolate YUN35 DNA cloned with ITS, LSU, and SSU primers.

ITS Blast results				
No.	NCBI Description , Y41	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i> strain CBS 113539 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	99.48	EU035435.1
2	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	99.31	EU035434.1
3	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene	99%	99.31	MT379576.1
4	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.46	KF766166.1
5	Uncultured <i>Fusicladium</i> clone MDD-OTU-26 18S ribosomal RNA gene	94%	99.64	KT581784.1
6	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 331.65 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	95.85	EU035469.1
7	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 120825 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	95.67	EU035468.1
8	<i>Fusicladium mandshuricum</i> strain CBS 112235 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	95.16	EU035433.1
9	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> culture-collection CBS:574.50 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	95.9	KF793784.1
10	<i>Venturia tremulae</i> var. <i>tremulae</i> strain CBS 257.38 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	94.99	EU035475.1
No.	NCBI Description , X14	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene	99%	99.83	MT379576.1
2	<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i> strain CBS 113539 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	99.83	EU035435.1
3	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	99.65	EU035434.1
4	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	97%	99.82	KF766166.1
5	Uncultured <i>Fusicladium</i> clone MDD-OTU-26 18S ribosomal RNA gene	95%	100	KT581784.1
6	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 331.65 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	96.18	EU035469.1

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7	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 120825 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	96.01	EU035468.1
8	<i>Fusicladium mandshuricum</i> strain CBS 112235 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	95.49	EU035433.1
9	<i>Venturia tremulae</i> var. <i>tremulae</i> strain CBS 257.38 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	95.32	EU035475.1
10	<i>Venturia ditricha</i> strain CBS 118894 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	95.32	EU035456.1
No.	NCBI Description , M10	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene	100%	100	MT379576.1
2	<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i> strain CBS 113539 18S ribosomal RNA gene,	100%	99.83	EU035435.1
3	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	99.65	EU035434.1
4	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	97%	99.82	KF766166.1
5	Uncultured <i>Fusicladium</i> clone MDD-OTU-26 18S ribosomal RNA gene	95%	100	KT581784.1
6	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 331.65 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	96.19	EU035469.1
7	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 120825 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	96.01	EU035468.1
8	<i>Fusicladium mandshuricum</i> strain CBS 112235 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	95.49	EU035433.1
9	<i>Venturia tremulae</i> var. <i>tremulae</i> strain CBS 257.38 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	95.33	EU035475.1
10	<i>Venturia ditricha</i> strain CBS 118894 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	95.33	EU035456.1
No.	NCBI Description , LS80	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene,	100%	99.83	MT379576.1
2	<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i> strain CBS 113539 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	99.65	EU035435.1
3	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	99.48	EU035434.1
4	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	97%	99.64	KF766166.1
5	Uncultured <i>Fusicladium</i> clone MDD-OTU-26 18S ribosomal RNA gene	95%	99.82	KT581784.1
6	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 331.65 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	96.03	EU035469.1
7	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 120825 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	95.85	EU035468.1
8	<i>Fusicladium mandshuricum</i> strain CBS 112235 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	95.34	EU035433.1
9	<i>Venturia tremulae</i> var. <i>tremulae</i> strain CBS 257.38 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	95.17	EU035475.1
10	<i>Venturia ditricha</i> strain CBS 118894 18S ribosomal RNA gene	100%	95.17	EU035456.1

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No.	NCBI Description , P2	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene	99%	99.31	MT379576.1
2	<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i> strain CBS 113539 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	99.13	EU035435.1
3	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	98.96	EU035434.1
4	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.29	KF766166.1
5	Uncultured <i>Fusicladium</i> clone MDD-OTU-26 18S ribosomal RNA gene	95%	99.46	KT581784.1
6	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 331.65 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	95.5	EU035469.1
7	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 120825 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	95.33	EU035468.1
8	<i>Fusicladium mandshuricum</i> strain CBS 112235 18S ribosomal RNA gene	99%	94.81	EU035433.1
9	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> strain Cam1 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene	84%	99.8	MN038075.1
10	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 379.35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene	96%	95.7	MH855709.1
LSU blast results				
No.	NCBI Description , Y41	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	97%	99.89	MT379577.1
2	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	97%	99.68	EU035434.1
3	<i>Venturia chlorospora</i> voucher Kruys 502 (UPS) large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	98.84	DQ384101.1
4	<i>Venturia chlorospora</i> strain CBS 470.61 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial	97%	99.25	EU035454.1
5	<i>Fusicladium peltigericola</i> strain VKM F-4740 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	97%	99.24	MF494608.1
6	<i>Fusicladium convolvularum</i> strain CBS 112706 28S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	97%	99.14	EU035428.1
7	<i>Venturia effusa</i> strain albino chromosome 7, complete sequence	99%	98.52	CP042191.1
8	<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i> strain CBS 113539 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	95%	99.78	EU035435.1
9	<i>Fusicladium peltigericola</i> culture-collection CBS:128206 18S ribosomal RNA gene	97%	99.03	HQ599579.2
10	<i>Venturia nashicola</i> strain CBS 793.84 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	96%	99.13	EU035465.1
No.	NCBI Description , X14	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.68	MT379577.1

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2	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	97%	99.89	EU035434.1
3	<i>Venturia chlorospora</i> strain CBS 470.61 18S ribosomal RNA gene	97%	99.46	EU035454.1
4	<i>Fusicladium peltigericola</i> strain VKM F-4740 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene	97%	99.45	MF494608.1
5	<i>Fusicladium convolvularum</i> strain CBS 112706 28S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	97%	99.35	EU035428.1
6	<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i> strain CBS 113539 18S ribosomal RNA gene	95%	100	EU035435.1
7	<i>Venturia chlorospora</i> voucher Kruys 502 (UPS) large subunit ribosomal RNA gene	98%	99.03	DQ384101.1
8	<i>Fusicladium peltigericola</i> culture-collection CBS:128206 18S ribosomal RNA gene	97%	99.24	HQ599579.2
9	<i>Venturia nashicola</i> strain CBS 793.84 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.34	EU035465.1
10	<i>Venturia effusa</i> strain albino chromosome 7, complete sequence	98%	98.71	CP042191.1
No.	NCBI Description , M10	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.44	MT379577.1
2	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	98%	99.33	EU035434.1
3	<i>Venturia tremulae</i> var. <i>tremulae</i> strain CBS 257.38 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99	MH867456.1
4	<i>Venturia chlorospora</i> strain CBS 470.61 18S ribosomal RNA gene,	99%	98.88	EU035454.1
5	<i>Fusicladium peltigericola</i> strain VKM F-4740 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene	98%	98.88	MF494608.1
6	<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i> strain CBS 113539 18S ribosomal RNA gene	97%	99.43	EU035435.1
7	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> strain CBS 331.65 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	98.77	MH870232.1
8	<i>Venturia nashicola</i> isolate HBCL1-16-1 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	98.77	MT845777.1
9	<i>Venturia nashicola</i> isolate HBCL1-14-1 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	98.77	MT845776.1
10	<i>Venturia nashicola</i> isolate HBCL1-16-5 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	98.77	MT845775.1
No.	NCBI Description , LS80	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	100	MT379577.1
2	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.89	EU035434.1
3	<i>Venturia chlorospora</i> strain CBS 470.61 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.45	EU035454.1
4	<i>Fusicladium peltigericola</i> strain VKM F-4740 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.45	MF494608.1

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5	<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i> strain CBS 113539 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	97%	100	EU035435.1
6	<i>Fusicladium convolvularum</i> strain CBS 112706 28S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.34	EU035428.1
7	<i>Fusicladium peltigericola</i> culture-collection CBS:128206 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.23	HQ599579.2
8	<i>Venturia chlorospora</i> voucher Kruys 502 (UPS) large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.23	DQ384101.1
9	<i>Venturia tremulae</i> var. <i>tremulae</i> strain CBS 257.38 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.56	MH867456.1
10	<i>Venturia nashicola</i> strain CBS 793.84 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.34	EU035465.1
No.	NCBI Description , P2	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Fusicladium phillyreae</i> strain CBS 113539 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.78	EU035435.1
2	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.67	EU035434.1
3	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 large subunit ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.78	MT379577.1
4	<i>Venturia tremulae</i> strain VKM F-4742 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.33	MF494610.1
5	<i>Venturia tremulae</i> var. <i>tremulae</i> strain CBS 257.38 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.33	EU035475.1
6	<i>Venturia ditricha</i> strain CBS 118894 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.33	EU035456.1
7	<i>Fusicladium peltigericola</i> strain VKM F-4740 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.22	MF494608.1
8	<i>Venturia viennotii</i> strain CBS 690.85 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.22	EU035476.1
9	<i>Venturia polygoni-vivipari</i> strain CBS 114207 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.22	EU035466.1
10	<i>Venturia lonicerae</i> strain CBS 445.54 18S ribosomal RNA gene	96%	99.22	EU035461.1
LSU blast results				
No.	NCBI Description , Y41	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.9	MT379578.1
2	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> isolate ATCC 60070 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.52	EF114737.1
3	<i>Uncultured Pezizomycotina</i> clone D0735_53_M small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.43	EU647053.1
4	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> isolate ATCC 38995 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.43	EF114739.1
5	<i>Spilocaea oleagina</i> 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.52	AF338393.1

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6	<i>Fusicladium convolvularum</i> STE-U 3884 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.33	AY251124.1
7	<i>Venturia asperata</i> isolate ATCC 34052 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.14	EF114736.1
8	<i>Phaeoramularia hachijoensis</i> STE-U 5391 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.14	AY251123.1
9	<i>Helicoon fuscosporum</i> strain UAMH 8757 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.14	AY856946.1
10	<i>Venturia effusa</i> strain albino chromosome 7, complete sequence	99%	99.05	CP042191.1
No.	NCBI Description , X14	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.71	MT379578.1
2	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> isolate ATCC 60070 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.71	EF114737.1
3	Uncultured <i>Pezizomycotina</i> clone D0735_53_M small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.62	EU647053.1
4	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> isolate ATCC 38995 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.62	EF114739.1
5	<i>Spilocaea oleagina</i> 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.62	AF338393.1
6	<i>Fusicladium convolvularum</i> STE-U 3884 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.52	AY251124.1
7	<i>Venturia asperata</i> isolate ATCC 34052 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.33	EF114736.1
8	<i>Phaeoramularia hachijoensis</i> STE-U 5391 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.33	AY251123.1
9	<i>Venturia effusa</i> strain albino chromosome 7, complete sequence	99%	99.23	CP042191.1
10	<i>Metacoleroa dickiei</i> isolate medipc 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.23	EF114719.1
No.	NCBI Description , M10	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.72	MT379578.1
2	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> isolate ATCC 60070 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.53	EF114737.1
3	Uncultured <i>Pezizomycotina</i> clone D0735_53_M small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.43	EU647053.1
4	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> isolate ATCC 38995 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.43	EF114739.1

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5	<i>Spilocaea oleagina</i> 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	97%	99.53	AF338393.1
6	<i>Fusicladium convolvularum</i> STE-U 3884 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.34	AY251124.1
7	<i>Venturia asperata</i> isolate ATCC 34052 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.15	EF114736.1
8	<i>Phaeoramularia hachijoensis</i> STE-U 5391 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.15	AY251123.1
9	<i>Venturia effusa</i> strain albino chromosome 7, complete sequence	98%	99.05	CP042191.1
10	<i>Metacoleroa dickiei</i> isolate medipc 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.05	EF114719.1
No.	NCBI Description , LS80	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.9	MT379578.1
2	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> isolate ATCC 60070 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.61	EF114737.1
3	Uncultured <i>Pezizomycotina</i> clone D0735_53_M small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.52	EU647053.1
4	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> isolate ATCC 38995 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.52	EF114739.1
5	<i>Spilocaea oleagina</i> 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.52	AF338393.1
6	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	97%	99.8	KF766251.1
7	<i>Fusicladium convolvularum</i> STE-U 3884 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.42	AY251124.1
8	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> strain CBS 594.70 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	97%	99.71	GU296205.1
9	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> strain CBS 815.69 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	97%	99.71	GU296204.1
10	<i>Venturia asperata</i> isolate ATCC 34052 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.23	EF114736.1
No.	NCBI Description , P2	Query cover	Per. ident	Accession
1	<i>Venturia oleaginea</i> isolate YUN35 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	100%	99.9	MT379578.1
2	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> isolate ATCC 60070 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.71	EF114737.1
3	<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> strain CBS 113427 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial	99%	99.71	KF766251.1

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	sequence			
4	Uncultured <i>Pezizomycotina</i> clone D0735_53_M small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.61	EU647053.1
5	<i>Venturia pyrina</i> isolate ATCC 38995 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.61	EF114739.1
6	<i>Spilocaea oleagina</i> 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.61	AF338393.1
7	<i>Fusicladium convolvularum</i> STE-U 3884 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	99%	99.51	AY251124.1
8	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> strain CBS 594.70 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.8	GU296205.1
9	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> strain CBS 815.69 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.8	GU296204.1
10	<i>Venturia populina</i> strain CBS 256.38 18S small subunit ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence	98%	99.7	GU296206.1

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S3. Effect of media types and other environmental factors on inducing *V. oleaginea* sporulation. F: few exist and not easy to account in the ordinary hemocytometer, conidia concentration: $+>10^4/\text{ml}$; $1 \times 10^4/\text{ml} \geq ++>1.5 \times 10^4/\text{ml}$, $1.5 \times 10^4/\text{ml} \geq +++ >4 \times 10^4/\text{ml}$, $++++ < 4 \times 10^4/\text{ml}$.

Treatment media, 80 plates for each treatment	1 st check for Sporulation in Strains Yun41, P2. Five plates opened for each treatment, 30 DAI. Incubate at 20 C	2 nd check, Two weeks of Light/dark 12:12 hrs, with Temp. fluctuation 15 C in light, 10 C in the dark, Five plates opened for each treatment	3 rd check for sporulation, 14 days under UV radiation And 60 DAI, In strains: Yun41, P2 Five plates opened, Incubate at 20 C	4 th check for sporulation one week after Scratching and 80 DAI.
1- Olive leaves media (OL)	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
OL+ oleic acid	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
OL+ oleic acid+ Casamino acid	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
OL+ oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
2- Pine needles agar media (PN) (0)	3/5F, 2/5F	1/5 F, 0/5	5/5,5/5++++	N/A
PN + oleic acid (1)	1/5 F, 0/5	0/5 , 0/5	4/5,4/5++	
PN + oleic acid+ Casamino acid(2)	2/5 F, 0/5	0/5 , 0/5	4/5,4/5++	
PN + oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin.(3)	1/5 F, 1/5 F	0/5 , 0/5 Most conidia diappear again	3/5,3/5+	
3- PN +OL : (PNOL) (0)	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	4/5+,4/5++	N/A
(PNOL) + oleic acid (1)	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	2/5+,2/5+	
(PNOL) + oleic acid+ Casamino acid(2)	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	2/5+,2/5+	
(PNOL) + oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin.				

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	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	3/5+,2/5++	
4- (1/10 strength PDA)	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
1/10 PDA+ oleic acid	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
1/10 PDA + oleic acid+ Casamino acid	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
1/10 PDA + oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
5- (1/10 strength PDA)+OL: (PDAOL)	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
(PDAOL)+ oleic acid	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
(PDAOL)+ oleic acid+ Casamino acid	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
(PDAOL)+ oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/5	0/5 ,0/50	0/5 ,0/50
6- Agar (control)	0/5,0/5	0/5,0/50	0/5,0/5	0/5,0/50
Agar + oleic acid+ Casamino acid+ Biotin.	0/5,0/5	0/5,0/50	0/5,0/5	0/5,0/50

S4. Chemical compounds synthesized by 14 Secondary gene clusters found using AntiSmash software.

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N.	SMS gene clusters	Compound(s)
1	TERPENE	squalestatin S1
2	TERPENE	carotenoid
3	TERPENE	swainsonine
4	TERPENE	ochrindole A
5	TERPENE	terrequinone A
6	T1PKS	pyripyropene A
7	T1PKS	sespendole
8	T1PKS	demethoxyviridin
9	T1PKS	alternariol
10	T1PKS	fumagillin, β -trans-bergamotene, fumagillol
11	T1PKS	aspernidgulene A1, aspernidgulene A2, aspernidgulene B1
12	T1PKS	naphthalene alternapyrone B, alternapyrone C, alternapyrone D, alternapyrone E, alternapyrone F
13	T1PKS	emodin
14	T1PKS	asparasone A
15	T1PKS	citreooviridin
16	T1PKS	grayanic acid
17	T1PKS	melanin
18	T1PKS	1,3,6,8-tetrahydroxynaphthalene
19	T1PKS	ACT-Toxin II
20	T1PKS	pyranonigrin E
21	T1PKS	3-(2'-hydroxy-3'-oxo-4'-methylpentyl)-indole
22	T1PKS	TAN-1612, 1-(2,3,5,10-tetrahydroxy-7-methoxy-4-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroanthracen-2-yl)pentane-2,4-dione, desmethyl TAN-1612
23	T1PKS	RES-1214-2
24	T1PKS	naphthopyrone
25	T1PKS	fusarin
26	T1PKS	F9775A, F9775B, orsellinic acid
27	T1PKS	depudecin
28	T1PKS	bikaverin
29	T1PKS	AF-toxin
30	NRPS-LIKE	sespendole
31	NRPS-LIKE	polysaccharide B
32	NRPS-LIKE	nidulanin A
33	NRPS-LIKE	iodinin
34	NRPS-LIKE	ferrichrome
35	NRPS-LIKE	myxoprincomide-c506
36	NRPS-LIKE	kolossin
37	NRPS-LIKE	curacomycin
38	NRPS-LIKE	HC-toxin
39	NRPS-LIKE	

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40	NRPS-LIKE	massetolide A
41	NRPS-LIKE	hexadecyhydroastechrome, terezine-D, astechrome
42	NRPS-LIKE	cyclo-(D-Phe-L-Phe-D-Val-L-Val)
43	NRPS-LIKE	tacrolimus
44	NRPS-LIKE	aspergillic acid
45	NRPS-LIKE	salinichelins
46	NRPS-LIKE	vicibactin
47	NRPS-LIKE	okaramine B
48	NRPS-LIKE	fusarielin H
49	NRPS	colicin V
50	NRPS	pentabromopseudilin
51	NRPS	basidioferrin
52	NRPS	tundrenone
53	NRPS	bromopyrroles/bromophenols
54	NRPS	notoamide A
55	NRPS	cylindrospermopsin
56	NRPS	Virginiafactin
57	NRPS	fragin
58	NRPS	pyrrolizixenamide A
59	NRPS	icosalide A, icosalide B
60	NRPS	isonitrile lipopeptides
61	NRPS	asperphenamate
62	NRPS	anabaenopeptin NZ857, nostamide A
63	NRPS	AM-toxin
64	NRPS	dimethylcoprogen
65	NRPS	serinocyclin A, serinocyclin B
66	NRPS	celesticetin
67	NRPS	livipeptin
68	NRPS	bicornutin A1, bicornutin A2
69	NRPS	xenotetrapeptide
70	NRPS	luminmide
71	NRPS	shinorine, 4-deoxygadusol, mycosporine glycine
72	NRPS	pseudomonine
73	NRPS	penicillin
74	NRPS	indigoidine
75	NRPS	exochelin
76	NRPS	ergovaline
77	NRPS	beauvericin
78	NRPS	AbT1
79	INDOLE	nodulisporic acid F viridicatumtoxin, previridicatumtoxin, 5-hydroxyanthrotainin, 8-O-
80	INDOLE	desmethylanthrotainin

Acknowledgment

First of all, my great thanks to Almighty Allah, Who helped me to complete this uphill task. Also, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my respectful supervisor Prof. ZongHua Wang for his unlimited support during my study period. I would be forever grateful to him for this person who taught me a lot, not only with his academic supervision but also in the various aspects of life. My heart will always have respect and affection for him.

Besides, I would like to acknowledge the special efforts of Dr. BaoHua Wang for her assistance during my Ph.D., which has a significant impact on my progress, and Doctor Jiandong Bao, who helped me in bioinformatics work. And really thankful to Prof. Stefan Olsson, his valuable notes helped me a lot in my experiments.

My sincere thanks goes to my fellow lab mates (Deming Yang, Qiushi Chen, Peng Chen Gbin, Wilfred Anjago, and many others who helped me, and for the great memories will lasting forever.

I am grateful to the Chinese government and Fujian Agriculture and Forestry University for providing me a scholarship for the doctoral degree.

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